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ASSESSMENTS OF MOLECULAR, MORPHOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS AMONG FOUR GENERA OF MUSHROOMS

A Dissertation

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Summary

A wide range of wild mushrooms inhabit natural ecosystems, generally in reaction to specific environmental conditions. Wild mushroom species are integral to the steppe and mountain ecosystems in Kurdistan Region of Iraq. Despite extensive investigation, the evolutionary relationships among the various strains remain mostly unknown. Furthermore, edible wild mushrooms contain substances that are nutritionally and biologically important for human consumption. There is a growing trend in the use of functional foods and traditional medicines derived from macro fungi owing to their numerous health benefits and rich nutrient contents. However, there remains a substantial gap in detailed scientific knowledge. Three molecular techniques were tested on sixty-three samples, including one farmed strain and sixty-two wild strains, for identification and genetic diversity as the first objective. This study also aimed to analyze the morpho-biochemical and chemical composition profiles and also evaluate the possible health benefits and risks of its biochemical constituents in cultivated and wild edible mushroom species collected from the Iraqi Kurdistan region. Phylogenetic analysis using Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) sequences identified two primary clades. A substantial aggregation of taxa was associated with the genera *Agaricus*, *Agrocybe*, *Pleurotus* and *Amanita*. A total of 373 polymorphic fragments were identified using markers such as conserved DNA-derived polymorphism (CDDP) and start codon target (SCoT). The CDDP and SCoT markers exhibited effects analogous to those of genetic diversity indices across several genera and species of mushrooms. CDDP exhibited a greater level of species-specific variance (23.74%) than SCoT markers (20.81%). CDDP (17 bands) and the SCoT (14.08 bands) markers exhibited high numbers of polymorphic bands per primer. The average polymorphism information content was 0.39 for both the CDDP and SCoT markers. In the clustering analysis, both methodologies categorized sixty-three samples into seven distinct groups. Three classes of mushroom species and genera were delineated using both markers. *Amanita lividopallescens* and *Agrocybe aegerita* showed the greatest genetic distance (0.48) for CDDP markers, while *Agrocybe aegerita* and *Pleurotus columbinus* showed the highest genetic dissimilarity (0.36) for SCoT markers. The combinatorial methods could effectively tell the difference between different strains of mushrooms. The significant genotypic diversity and sequenced genomes will offer an ideal basis for functional genomics studies of the mushroom strains. Significant variations were observed among the studied species in the morpho-biochemical characters. *Amanita crocea* (73.74 g), *Amanita lividopallescens* (58.54 g), and *Amanita vittadinii* (60.57 g) exhibited the highest mushroom weights. *Pleurotus eryngii* had the largest cap diameter (10.70 cm vertical, 9.04 cm horizontal). Wild species showed significantly higher biochemical traits, except for moisture content. The chemical composition

profiles varied among the species. Several bioactive compounds with health and pharmaceutical properties have been identified. Cultivated species contained the lowest number of compounds. *Amanita lividopallescens* had the highest concentrations of 9-octadecenoic acid (16.56%), 13-octadecenoic acid-methyl ester (11.15%), ergosterol (14.62%), and hexadecanoic acid-methyl ester (10.13%). Multivariate analysis grouped the 11 species into three major clusters. Nine potentially harmful compounds were detected in eight species. The study concludes that substantial variations existed in the traits examined among mushroom species. Wild species demonstrated superior biochemical traits and chemical compositions compared with cultivated mushroom. By emphasizing research and cultivation methods, the potential of mushrooms as crucial components of nutrition and medicine can be realized, positively impacting health outcomes and contributing to sustainable agricultural practices.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Eukaryotic heterotrophs called fungi, which have an estimated million species and are considered to be of tremendous economic and ecological importance (Blackwell, 2011; Hibbett *et al.*, 2016). The distribution of many fungal species is quite extensive, and it is possible that some of these species are truly cryptic or comprised of numerous genetic lineages. Mushrooms are interesting fruiting structures of specialized fungi that possess enormous fruiting bodies and have complex development (Joseph, 2021; Terry *et al.*, 2023). Mushrooms are members of the fungi kingdom and are referred to as macro fungi. All these organisms exist in different terrestrial biomes and are best exhibited in forests, where they have a functional abundance coupled with numerous important ecological functions. Various types of mushrooms have been known to establish symbiotic relationships with plants, in which case they are useful, and they also have important role as coprophytic fungi, where they decompose organic materials and nutrients (Dance, 2017). The fruiting bodies of macro fungi were vulnerable to environmental influences; therefore, morphological assessments typically cannot identify closely related genetic groupings (Zhao *et al.*, 2016). In the life cycle of *Basidiomycetes* and certain *Ascomycetes*, mushrooms are seen as visible fungi with unique carpophores, also called basidiocarps or fruiting bodies. They can be edible, inedible, or poisonous, and they are morphologically characterized as stinkhorns, puffballs, brackets, and gilled fungi (Adeniyi *et al.*, 2018). Mushrooms, which are fruiting bodies that develop from a subterranean mycelium and are widely consumed around the world, are produced by certain members of the macro-fungi group (Kalač, 2013). Rural areas and developing nations often gather wild mushrooms for culinary purposes or economic gain (Boa, 2004 ; Kotowski, 2016). Meanwhile, a select few mushroom species are farmed commercially and sold worldwide. The current culinary trends that prioritize health and sustainability are well aligned with mushrooms; thus, they are gaining in popularity. In reality, they are suitable for vegetarian diets, have ideal nutritional properties, and are compatible with a sustainable food supply (Giusti *et al.*, 2020).

Cultivated mushrooms are widely imported for Iraqi Kurdistan since mushroom growing cannot meet the high national demand. Wild mushrooms, on the other hand, have a long history of recreational collecting in Iraqi Kurdistan, and their users tend to value them more than the cultivated varieties. The months in concern are designated for this gathering. Mushrooms are not completely risk-free to eat. As a matter of fact, poisoning from mushrooms is a major kind of toxin-induced illness that can impact the neurological, respiratory, digestive, and liver systems (Giusti *et al.*, 2021; Govorushko *et al.*, 2019). When very toxic species are present, the liver sustains permanent damage that can be lethal. In addition, there are edible species that, if not handled correctly during collection,

transportation, storage, and cooking, might turn hazardous (Gawlikowski *et al.*, 2015; Nieminen and Mustonen, 2020b). They thrive on a variety of substrates and are often abundant during the rainy season in most regions. The many ecological, nutritional, physiological, and medicinal benefits of mushrooms have earned them the status of important bioresources (Ayimbila and Keawsompong, 2023). They help the ecosystem with nutrient recycling by breaking down dead organic materials, especially those that include lignin and cellulose (Kumla *et al.*, 2020). In addition to being rich in protein, crude fiber, vitamins, and minerals, they also have medicinal properties that make them useful in treating a variety of conditions, including high cholesterol, tumors, infections, cancer, ageing, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, antihyperglycemic, antiparasitic, anti-inflammatory, and antihypertensive conditions (Bhambri *et al.*, 2022).

Although cultivated mushrooms have a large following, wild mushrooms have a unique appeal and potential for enormous growth in the food industry (Barua *et al.*, 2024; Zhao, 2023). Almost all wild mushrooms are deemed useful to humans, are accepted as being very beneficial to the immune system, and have powerful antioxidants (Ao and Deb, 2019; Sun *et al.*, 2017). Certain species of mushrooms can be cooked in a wide variety of recipes, although many fungi are extremely poisonous. There are also other types of mushrooms that are known to be psychoactive, which means that they can change the recipients' state of mind or do some other form of harm to humans or other organisms (Ab Rhaman *et al.*, 2021; Mattos-Shiple *et al.*, 2016).

The majority of morphological and agronomic features, however, are quantitative variables that are highly responsive to environmental variation (Tahir *et al.*, 2021). Consequently, the genetic variety of germplasm resources cannot be directly reflected by phenotypic data (Lin *et al.*, 2022a; Rokni *et al.*, 2019). Fungal morphological traits are highly variable and influenced by environmental factors, leading to overlapping or indistinct features among genetically distinct groups, as evidenced by the lack of consistent morphological traits among molecularly defined fungal species and intraspecific groups (Lin *et al.*, 2023). Conventional methods for identifying fungal species are typically characterized by indiscrimination, inconsistent morphology, and inconspicuousness; however, modern molecular techniques have mitigated these issues. For precise species identification of mushrooms, however, DNA analysis in conjunction with phenotypic data is preferred because of its speed and low cost. Analyses using PCR-amplified nuclear rRNA genes, and more specifically the Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) region, which has been selected as a DNA barcode identifier for fungi because of its significant interspecies variation, constitute the majority of current approaches. The small subunit 5.8S rRNA gene separates the two non-coding parts (ITS-1 and ITS-2), which are in the ITS region and are about 600 to 800 bp in size. Genome sequencing at this marker and subsequent comparison to publicly available reference DNA libraries constitute the highest standard for taxonomic identification (Badotti *et al.*, 2017; Creedy *et al.*, 2020; Lücking *et al.*, 2020). In the

past, different researchers employed molecular techniques for the identification and estimation of genetic variation within different mushroom strains (An *et al.*, 2021; Jiao *et al.*, 2024; Lin *et al.*, 2022a; Liu *et al.*, 2018; Rokni *et al.*, 2019; Zhao *et al.*, 2016). The use of conserved DNA-derived polymorphism (CDDP) molecular markers is capable of capturing information uniquely offered by the targeted application of a single primer to a single locus within a gene of transcription factors (Ahmed *et al.*, 2023; Aziz and Tahir, 2023; Tahir *et al.*, 2023).

Many studies have used SCoT markers, which are usually polymorphic and depend on shorter conserved regions close to the ATG start codon, to uncover genetic diversity and aid in conservation efforts. In this technique, similar to RAPD or ISSR markers, a single primer acts as both the forward and reverse primer (Tahir *et al.*, 2023). The chemical characteristics were offered as supplementary criteria to better delineate species that have received more attention than before. The amount of phenolic and flavonoid compounds found in mushrooms serves as a reason for the quantity of antioxidants present within their bodies. These substances greatly increase the nutritional value of mushrooms, but they can also be used for the treatment of ailments, such as inflammation and cancer (Latif *et al.*, 2024). Isolation and quantification of bioactive metabolites from wild mushrooms can be achieved using an analytical method known as gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (GC/MS). Several compounds with antiviral, anticancer, and antimicrobial activities, including fatty acids, phenols, and other secondary metabolites, have recently been isolated from mushrooms using GC/MS (Fogarasi *et al.*, 2024 ; Rijia *et al.*, 2024). Our literature review reveals an absence of published data about the in-silico analysis of the frequency of CDDP and SCoT markers across all fungal genomes. To our knowledge, this is a novel occurrence both regionally and globally for certain species. Iraqi Kurdistan possesses a wealth of mushroom genetic resources, despite having only one cultivated species. The presence of several names for identical or closely related strains results in difficulties in classification and ambiguity concerning genetic distinctiveness and relationships among strains. These challenges have complicated the categorization and preservation of genetic resources, the selection of appropriate breeding parents, and the advancement of improved cultivars. Therefore, the assessment of genetic diversity and the appraisal of germplasm resources are thus crucial. This comprehensive approach enabled the analysis of genetic variation data and improved understanding of the genetic diversity present in the germplasm resources from 63 mushroom strains. To fully comprehend the potential of wild mushrooms and to strengthen their preservation, more research in this area is required. In this view, we assessed sixty-three mushroom strains (62 wild and 1 cultivated) from the Iraqi Kurdistan region for identification using nuclear gene (Internal Transcribed Spacer) marker. We applied CDDP and SCoT markers to evaluate genetic diversity and differentiation among the diverse species and genera of wild mushrooms. This comprehensive approach enabled the analysis of genetic variation data and improved understanding of the genetic diversity present in the

germplasm resources from sixty-three mushroom strains. The identification of superior genetic resources established an outline for subsequent research aimed at enhancing and broadening current germplasm resources and breeding materials. In addition, in this study, we analyzed the genetic variation at levels of morpho-biochemical and chemical composition in cultivate and wild mushroom collection from different regions of Iraq's Kurdistan and evaluated the possible health benefits and risks of its biochemical constituents. This study will help in the appropriate selection of mushrooms that researchers are interested in and mushrooms that are believed to possess bioactivity and need to be dealt with sensitively to prevent harm. In summary, the combination of GC/MS profiling, genetic diversity measurement, and analysis of the other components, such as sugars, proteins, phenolics, and flavonoids, provides a more complete understanding of wild mushrooms. This sophisticated exploration contributes greatly to our understanding of the biological and ecological significance of mushrooms and widens their importance as bioactive agents in medicine and other sciences. More work in this direction must be done to understand the full potential of wild mushrooms and to consolidate their preservation.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 History and Taxonomy of Mushrooms

People have been consuming mushrooms for thousands of years, appreciating them for their nutritional, medicinal, and spiritual value. The ancient Egyptians considered mushrooms as tokens of immortality, and accounts of medicinal fungi such as *Ganoderma lucidum* were recorded in traditional Chinese medicine over 2000 years ago (Singh *et al.*, 2025). Psychoactive mushrooms were also used in religious ceremonies of Mesoamerican indigenous cultures (Haro-Luna *et al.*, 2025). Mycology, the scientific study of fungi, developed rapidly in the 17th century with the roots reaching back to the works of Pier Antonio Micheli. Nowadays, beyond mushrooms being prized for their food and medicine, an explicit appreciation of their ecopoetic contribution to the world's ecosystems, which has flourished alongside the molecular revolution, which has expanded our understanding of fungal diversity (Wijayawardene *et al.*, 2020). Fungi and mushrooms belong to the Kingdom Fungi, a different kingdom of life than plants, animals and protists.

Most of the edible and medicinal mushrooms belong to Basidiomycota phylum, and more specifically to Agaricomycetes class, including the popular genera of *Agaricus*, *Pleurotus*, *Lentinula* and *Ganoderma* (He *et al.*, 2019). In addition, some edible species (i.e. *Morchella*, *Tuber*) are included in the phylum Ascomycota. The kingdom Fungi includes mushrooms, which mainly consist of the Phylum Basidiomycota with its spores produced on a specialized structure called a basidium and to a lesser extent the Phylum Ascomycota but its spores form inside asci. Traditional taxonomy emphasizes morphological features such as the shape of fruiting bodies, spore color and hyphal structure (Wijayawardene *et al.*, 2024). However, recent molecular studies, particularly those employing Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) sequencing, have largely shown that morphology by itself is insufficient for accurate classification. Therefore, modern taxonomy is using an integrative approach: morphological, ecological, biochemical and molecule data are combined to build a better evolutionary framework for mushroom classification (Varga *et al.*, 2019). Wild Mushroom also known as macro fungi is the fruiting bodies of fungi that grow in natural environments, such as forest, grassland. They play a crucial part in passing nutrients on: Either they take them from plants as part of a symbiotic relationship (mycorrhizae), or they are decomposers which feed off dead organic matter. Wild mushrooms are bountiful: Over 14,000 species have been described, and the ecological, nutritional and medicinal effects of some species are hot topics for much research (Bahram and Netherway, 2022). Many species such as *Agaricus bisporus* (common button mushroom),

Cantharellus cibarius (chanterelle), are highly regarded for their culinary value and justifications, while *Ganoderma lucidum* (reishi) and *Cordyceps sinensis* are well known bioactive elements with significant future potential (Eshita *et al.*, 2024).

Major Categories for each Genus:

1) Agaricus Genus

Kingdom	Fungi
Division	Basidiomycota
Class	Agaricomycetes
Order	Agaricales
Family	Agaricaceae
Genus	Agaricus
Species	Bisporus, Litoralis, Campestris & Pseudolutosus

2) Agrocybe Genus

Kingdom	Fungi
Division	Basidiomycota
Class	Agaricomycetes
Order	Agaricales
Family	Strophariaceae
Genus	Agrocybe
Species	Aegerita & Dura

3) Amanita Genus

Kingdom	Fungi
Division	Basidiomycota
Class	Agaricomycetes
Order	Agaricales
Family	Amanitaceae
Genus	Amanita
Species	Vittadinii, Lividopallescens & Crocea

4) Pleurotus Genus

Kingdom	Fungi
Division	Basidiomycota

Class	Agaricomycetes
Order	Agaricales
Family	Pleurotaceae
Genus	Pleurotus
Species	Eryngii & Columbinus

2.2 Economic Importance of Mushroom

Economically, wild mushrooms are one of the major non-wood forest products, (i.e. *Tuber Melanosporum* (black truffle) and *Morchella esculenta* (morel) that are sold in the international markets; because of being considered precious food (Hall *et al.*, 2003). The expansion of the world market of mushrooms is gradually increasing with the increase of the demand of gourmet and functional foods around the world (Sangeeta *et al.*, 2024). Reishi (*Ganoderma lucidum*) and *Cordyceps sinensis* have been extensively examined for their biological active compounds which are polysaccharides, triterpenoids and antioxidants that have been confirmed to provide immune dilatory, anticancer and anti-inflammatory effects (Ekiz *et al.*, 2023). For instance, *Ganoderma lucidum* is a fungus whose traditional use dates back to ancient China and has also been confirmed by present-day scientific investigations for cancer treatment and immune system enhancement. *Cordyceps sinensis* also has potential for improving exercise capacity and combating fatigue. Besides the benefits mentioned above, overharvesting and loss of habitat can pose what is wild mushroom at risk therefore, there are compelling reasons for sustainable harvesting and conservation (Plosca *et al.*, 2025; Priyanka *et al.*, 2024).

2.3 Ecological Importance of Mushrooms

Fungi bearing mushrooms are crucial for ecological roles such as carrying out the role of a decomposer, symbiont and a pathogen. In nutrient cycling, they play a prominent role, especially in forest systems where they breakdown complex organic material (i.e., lignin and cellulose) to its constituent parts to make them available for absorption by plants, other fungi, and soil animals (Bahram and Netherway, 2022). These compounds are for the most part metabolized by exogenous enzymes such as lignin peroxidases and cellulases that are released by fungi that decompose plant cell walls. In addition to its role as a saprotroph (decomposer), many mushrooms are also involved in symbiotic or phototrophic relationships with plants through the formation of mutualistic mycorrhizal association. These mutualisms, in particular of ecto and arbuscular mycorrhiza, help plant uptake of nutrients, such as phosphorus and nitrogen, and the fungi receive carbohydrates from photosynthesis

(Wahab *et al.*, 2023). Exemplary ectomycorrhizal fungi belong to the genera *Amanita* or *Boletus*, colonizing the roots of trees, constituting a key component of forest dynamics and productivity (Rivera *et al.*, 2022). Mushrooms also display a great deal of ecological variation, with saprotrophic and parasitism being among the strategies of certain members of this group. These are well-studied fungi, and the parasites of *Armillaria mellea* and the is often causing root rot and having dramatic consequences both from an ecological and economic standpoint (Viret and Gindro, 2025).

Environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, and soil pH do not only influence the distribution and activity of mushrooms, but also temper their ecological roles (Somasundaram *et al.*, 2024). For example, climate change has been implicated as affecting the phenology and geographic range of the species of mushrooms, which could have cascading effects on the functioning of ecosystems (Carrie *et al.*, 2016). More generally, mushrooms play a role in maintaining biodiversity as they are habitat and a food source for a wide array of organisms from insects to mammals and to their fungi (Bahram and Netherway, 2022). In addition, they are involved in the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites, which are of ecological and pharmacological importance, including antibiotics and mycotoxins that mediate interspecies interactions (Wadhwa *et al.*, 2024). Even though very important from an ecological perspective, the majority of the mushroom species remain largely understudied, and nowhere is this truer than in the tropics and subtropics where mycological biodiversity is known to be extraordinarily high yet poorly documented and reported. In response to this, conservation interventions are key to the protection of these animals and their roles in ecosystems, especially as they are threatened by habitat loss and climate change (Wang *et al.*, 2022).

2.4 Nutritional and Medicinal Values and Healthy Risks of Mushrooms

They are also a rich source of essential macro and micronutrients and of a plethora of biologically active compounds, which probably mediate the health-protective effect of mushrooms. They are low in fat and calories, rich in top-quality protein comprising all the 9 essential amino acids, which makes them an excellent part of any diet, helpful for everybody but especially for vegetarians and vegans (Himanshi *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, mushrooms also supplied ranges of B vitamins, together with riboflavin (B2), niacin (B3) and pantothenic acid (B5), which carried out important functions within the metabolism of vitality, neural functioning, and well-being pores and skin maintenance (Miaoyu *et al.*, 2021). It is also a rich source of minerals, selenium, copper, potassium, and phosphorus. Selenium acts as a significant antioxidant that shields cells from the damage caused by free radicals, while copper plays a role in iron metabolism and supports the immune system (Assemie and Abaya, 2022). Mushrooms have the ability to produce vitamin D when they are exposed to ultraviolet (UV) light, making them one of the few non-animal sources of this vital nutrient. Vitamin D is essential for calcium absorption, the preservation of bone strength, and immune function (Cardwell *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, mushrooms are rich in bioactive compounds, including beta-glucans, ergothioneine,

and glutathione, all of which have been extensively researched for their health benefits. Beta-glucans, a type of soluble fiber, are known to boost immune responses, enhance gut health, and lower cholesterol levels (Jayachandran *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, the potent antioxidants ergothioneine and glutathione are present, and they are believed to help reduce oxidative stress and inflammation, potentially lowering the risk of chronic diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular conditions, and neurodegenerative disorders (Singh *et al.*, 2025). Mushrooms in the wild have been used in traditional medicine worldwide for thousands of years, although more recently have been characterized to reveal their promise as a class of bioactive molecules with immense therapeutic power.

The sole active principles responsible for these effects, i.e., polysaccharides (e.g., beta-glucans), terpenoids, phenolic compounds, ergosterol, and lectins that are found in these wild mushrooms are the major compounds driving interactions with human physiological systems in support of health and protection against several diseases (Harpreet *et al.*, 2022). They potentiate the effector functions of NK cells, macrophages and inhibit angiogenesis and metastasis in cancer cells (Reis-Sobreiro *et al.*, 2021). *Cordyceps sinensis* has acquired significant attention for improving respiratory function, physical capacity and anti-cancer activities. Bioactive compounds, such as polysaccharides and cordycepin, contained in it, have demonstrated to induce cancer cells apoptosis and regulate immune responses (Zhou *et al.*, 2009). Another distinguishing fungus, *Inonotus obliquus* (Chaga), has also been well-researched for its antioxidant/anti-inflammatory activities. Its rich supply of melanin and polyphenols effectively fight oxidative stress and have also been found useful in managing chronic disease conditions such as diabetes, cardiovascular diseases and cancer as well (Fordjour *et al.*, 2023). Several wild mushrooms have been found to possess antimicrobial activity and may be considered for the development of novel antibiotics in the face of increasing antimicrobial resistance. For example, oyster mushroom *Pleurotus ostreatus*, and shiitake mushroom, *Lentinula edodes* have bioactive peptides and phenolic substances that demonstrated antibacterial and antifungal activities (Yakobi *et al.*, 2023). Also, the turkey tail mushroom (*Trametes versicolor*) has recently gained interest with relation to polysaccharide-K (PSK) and polysaccharide-peptide (PSP) adjuvants in cancer therapy to boost immune reaction and reduce chemotherapy-related side effects (Habtemariam, 2020). Another point of high interest is in the antioxidant activity of wild mushrooms. Oxidative stress is one of the main factors implicated in the pathophysiology process of several chronic diseases, and several mushroom species, such as the sun mushroom (*Agaricus blazei*) and maitake mushroom (*Grifola frondosa*), have shown free radical scavenging, thereby decreasing oxidative damage. This effect has been assigned especially to their phenolic compounds and also an exceptional antioxidant, ergothioneine, abundant in fungi (Himanshi *et al.*, 2017).

Pesticides and heavy metals may gather up in mushrooms from their growing environment. Wild mushrooms have a higher risk of contamination, but commercially grown varieties may also be affected if controls are inadequate. It is critical to source from reliable vendors to prevent exposure to harmful substances. The primary health risk is inadvertently consuming toxic wild mushrooms, which can result in severe symptoms of poisoning such as delirium, confusion, muscle spasms, and in extreme situations, organ failure or death. Correct mushroom identification is essential because eating mushrooms from dubious sources or foraging without knowledge raises the risk of poisoning. For sensitive people, mushrooms can trigger allergic reactions ranging from minor rashes or itching in the mouth to severe anaphylaxis. Individuals who already have food allergies, Mold allergies, asthma, or weakened immune systems may be at greater risk. Since raw mushrooms contain chitin and mild toxins that affect digestion, cooking them can lower some sensitivity risks (Lee *et al.*, 2019; Orywal *et al.*, 2021; Patryk *et al.*, 2021). For instance, amatoxins found in the "death cap" mushroom (*Amanita phalloides*) can cause multi-organ failure and fatal liver damage. After six to twelve hours of delayed symptoms, there may be severe gastrointestinal distress (diarrhea, vomiting), liver and kidney damage, and occasionally the need for a liver transplant. Orellanine causes kidney failure with symptoms that appear weeks later, while other toxins like muscarine cause cholinergic symptoms. These mushrooms can cause poisoning that is either fatal or life-threatening (Tran *et al.*, 2025). False morels, or *Gyromitra* species, contain gyromitrin toxin, which can result in seizures, vomiting, diarrhea, and possibly even liver failure (Horowitz *et al.*, 2025; Vohra *et al.*, 2024).

2.5 Identification of Mushrooms

Their great relevance in ecological, evolutionary, and conservation biology is linked to the knowledge of adaptive potential, evolutionary history and resilience of populations to environmental changes. One of the important is the genetic diversity, which is the total of genetic characteristics in the genetic makeup of species (Yong *et al.*, 2025). Greater genetic diversity within a population enhances its ability to withstand disease as well as colonize new habitat types and can increase its robustness to stressors like climate change, habitat fragmentation and pollution (Sarah *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, understanding the species and their genetic lineages is crucial to effectively understanding patterns and processes of evolutionary relationships biogeography and speciation vs. hybridization (Sarah *et al.*, 2020).

2.5.1 Morphological identification

Morphological systematics typically serves as the initial approach for exploring the ecological aspects related to the genetic and taxonomic diversity of fungi. It is the comprehensive analysis of the macro- and micromorphological characters of the fungus (Wijayawardene *et al.*, 2024). Macroscopic

features commonly recorded include cap (pileus) size, shape, surface (texture, such as smooth or scaly), margin characteristics, color changes with aging, and the presence of such structures as universal or partial veils. Some other external characters are the shape and size of stipe (stem), the existence of a ring (annulus) and volva, the gill attachment (free, adnexed, adnate, decurrent), spacing and color of lamellae, and the color of spore print (Sánchez *et al.*, 2020). Identification can tentatively be made by preimaginal grouping into genera or species complexes based on external morphology. Besides macroscopic observation and study, microscopic study is essential for discrimination between related or cryptic species, and among the microscopic features are the size, shape, ornamentation (smooth, warted, spiny) and color of the spores, the basidia number (2- or 4-sterigmate), the type of cystidia (cheilocystidia, pleurocystidia), and the hyphal system (monomitic, dimitic, trimitic) (Varga *et al.*, 2019). For better visualization of microstructures, special staining procedures, which are adapted specifically for either amyloid reactions or Congo red staining, are usually applied. However, even though it has been used for a long period of time, morphology identification has severe weaknesses. Phenotypic plasticity when a single genotype produces different morphologies under different environmental conditions frequently causes misidentification (Sánchez *et al.*, 2020). Morphological characteristics can be influenced by habitat, climate, and substrate and by the stage of development, making precise identification hard to achieve (Fakan *et al.*, 2024). In addition, in certain species morphological differences between them and their hosts are very small and can usually only be distinguished under expert and sophisticated microscopes. Finally, morphological comparison may not necessarily reflect genetic diversity, but it provides crucial information on which biochemical and molecular techniques can be built as a starting point.

2.5.2 Biochemical identification

Phytochemical markers involved in mushrooms phytochemical markers have been recognized as naturally occurring bioactive chemical compounds including secondary metabolites, phenolics, proteins, flavonoids and sugars, which are considered as a valuable tool for the differentiation of strains, therapeutic potential of mushrooms as well as taxonomic classification. In edible and medicinal species (particularly the *Lentinula edodes*, *Ganoderma lucidum*, and *Pleurotus ostreatus*, qualitative/quantitative phytochemical analyses such as total phenolic content (TPC), total flavonoid content (TFC), antioxidant capacity (DPPH/FRAP tests), soluble sugar, and crude protein content are often assessed to determine their respective biochemical profiles (Elhusseiny *et al.*, 2021; Mirsada *et al.*, 2021). These assays demonstrate not only the nutritional and pharmaceutical aspects of mushroom strains, but also selection of elite strains for breeding and mushroom production. For instance, phenolics and flavonoids are identified as powerful antioxidants, they participate in free radicals scavenging activities, while soluble sugars and proteins play crucial roles on metabolic

energy supply and as indicators of the quality of fruiting bodies (Cardoso *et al.*, 2021). Their concentrations vary according to species, substrate, developmental phase, and ecological context, making them valuable chemotaxonomic indicators. As a result, phytochemical profiling is now integrated with DNA-based molecular techniques to enhance understanding of the diversity and functionality of mushrooms (Khan *et al.*, 2023). Mushrooms also contain many other important biochemical compounds, particularly polysaccharides (β -glucans), sterols, terpenoids, and phenylpropanoids. Of these, β -glucans are by far the most widely studied in relation to their immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer effects, and they are routinely used as functional criteria in assessing not only the nutritional value of mushrooms but also in the breeding of new mushroom strains (Zade *et al.*, 2025). The biochemical composition of the mushrooms is very specific to species and depends on several parameters, such as substrate, growth, stage, climatic conditions, and geographical region. For example, mushrooms grown on lignocellulosic-rich media show generally higher phenolic and polysaccharide levels, while environmental stress, such as UV and water closure, increases antioxidant capacity (Cardoso *et al.*, 2021). Such diversity underscores the importance of biochemical markers in chemotaxonomy and the potential of facilitating strain and species discrimination using metabolite profiles. The GC-MS technique is a valuable approach for the separation, identification, and quantification of both volatile and semi-volatile compounds present in mushrooms. This method is essential for evaluating bioactive metabolites, such as sterols, fatty acids, alcohols, and phenolic derivatives (Williams *et al.*, 2021). Among the compounds frequently detected is ergosterol, which accounts for roughly 0.2% to 0.4% of the dry weight of mushrooms. It serves as a key indicator of fungal biomass and acts as a precursor to vitamin D₂ (Taofiq *et al.*, 2020). Another significant compound is Oct-1-en-3-ol, widely referred to as “Mushroom alcohol” which represents a primary volatile component in fresh mushrooms, making up over 60-70% of the overall volatile composition in species like *Agaricus bisporus* and *Pleurotus ostreatus* (Tonks *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, linoleic acid, identified as a polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA), can constitute 15% to 25% of the total fatty acids in mushrooms such as *Ganoderma lucidum* and *Lentinula edodes*, contributing significantly to their nutritional and medicinal properties (Pavel Kalač, 2009). Solid phase microextraction (SPME) and other sample preparation methods developed in recent times have tended to improve the potential of GC-MS analysis in mushroom studies. SPME-GC-MS focuses the analysis of volatile compounds extracted without solvents and paves the way to the analysis of those compounds at trace levels of which it is difficult to be detected (Keerthana *et al.*, 2024). Moreover, GC-MS has started to be combined with multivariate statistical techniques for discrimination between different fungal species on a metabolic level. This chemometric method facilitates the discrimination between morphologically similar species and the characterization of bioactive compounds for pharmaceutical and functional food applications (Fatih *et al.*, 2020).

2.5.3 Molecular identification

The internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region is widely acknowledged as a universal DNA barcode for fungi, including mushrooms, due to its notable variation at the species level and the simplicity of its amplification (Schoch *et al.*, 2012). In recent decades, molecular techniques utilizing ITS have been essential in assessing genetic diversity among mushroom species, assisting in the identification of both cultivated and wild varieties, which in turn supports breeding and selection efforts. Research on mushroom taxonomy has shown that ITS sequence data can reveal hidden diversity, closely related species, and instances of misidentification or new taxa within genera such as *Ganoderma*, *Pleurotus*, and *Agaricus* (Jargalmaa *et al.*, 2017; Zhang *et al.*, 2021; Zhao *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, ITS markers have been utilized in phylogenetic studies, shedding light on the evolutionary connections among morphologically similar species and helping in taxonomic revisions (Zheng *et al.*, 2025). In addition, the use of ITS data is becoming more prevalent in molecular ecology studies aimed at characterizing the diversity of fungal communities in various habitats, highlighting its importance in research on mushroom diversity (Wei *et al.*, 2023). Despite some limitations, such as restricted resolution in specific genera and intragenomic variability, the ITS region is still regarded as the most dependable marker for the molecular identification and classification of mushrooms (Nilsson *et al.*, 2019).

Overall, molecular markers derived from the ITS region have significantly advanced our understanding of genetic diversity in mushrooms, which carries vital implications for conservation efforts, breeding practices, and sustainable use. While the ITS region is effective for identifying species, its resolution can vary across different taxonomic groups. For instance, genera like *Russula* and *Cortinarius* may have ITS sequences that lack the necessary variability to distinguish closely related species clearly; thus, it is recommended to use these sequences alongside other loci (e.g., LSU, TEF1, RPB2) for phylogenetic studies (Frøslev *et al.*, 2005). The ITS region is the most frequently employed marker in environmental sequencing and fungal community studies. Research utilizing ITS1 and ITS2 metabarcoding has effectively revealed the diversity and composition of mushroom populations across various ecosystems, such as forest soils and decaying wood, and has aided in the identification of both cultivable and rare species (Tedersoo *et al.*, 2010). The success of ITS-based identification relies heavily on well-curated databases like UNITE, which offer reliable reference sequences for fungi. Furthermore, advancements in bioinformatics tools like QIIME2 and ITS have further refined the processes of filtering, aligning, and classifying ITS sequences, thereby increasing the accuracy of diversity assessments (Nilsson *et al.*, 2019).

Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) have become one of the most popular molecular markers for the analysis of genetic variations in fungi, including mushrooms. Due to their wide distribution throughout the genome, SNPs are common in wild and cultivated mushrooms and have been considered to be a useful molecular tool for studying population structure, evolutionary relationship

and genetic diversity (Diao *et al.*, 2024). The implementation of SNPs has enabled taxonomic, breeding, and conservation advances by distinguishing between specific strains and species (Wenne, 2023). Inter simple sequence repeat (ISSR) markers are widely used for diversity studies in fungi as these are easy to perform and do not require any prior knowledge of genomic information and polymorphisms can be easily and clearly detected (Gemmill and Grierson, 2021). Such markers are also used in distinguishing between fungal isolates and genetic diversity of wild edible mushrooms (Lin *et al.*, 2022b). Moreover, ISSR markers are used in taxonomic and ecological studies on marine-derived fungi and non-model fungi (Oliveira and Azevedo, 2022). Furthermore, ISSR has been successful in the study of genetic structure of *Ganoderma* species (Palanna *et al.*, 2022).

Simple sequence repeats (SSR), or microsatellites, have been proven to be valuable markers in fungal genetics due to their high degree of polymorphism, co-dominance in inheritance, and reproduction. SSR markers also are used for the studies of genetic diversity and population structure in mushrooms including *Agaricus bisporus* (An *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, SSRs have been utilized to investigate the evolution of fungi and the geographical distribution of fungi in natural populations (Lotus and Jason, 2021). In addition, SSRs are also useful for variety identification and to secure the genetic purity for both edible and medicinal species of mushrooms (Das *et al.*, 2013).

Conserved DNA-based derived polymorphism (CDDP) is a highly efficient and universal method applicable for all DNA marker approaches that have recently been applied to fungal genetics, particularly that of the higher fungi. This approach capitalizes on the conservation of nucleotide sequence between the families of genes encoding transcription factor genes and other functional regions across the fungal genomes, for amplification (Collard and Mackill, 2009). CDDP primers are constructed based on conserved amino acid motifs of frequently conserved genes that possess functional relevance and usually retained these motifs across fungal taxa (Chávez *et al.*, 2025). The major advantages of this strategy include its high reproducibility, and the elimination of the need for previous genomic sequencing, making it particularly convenient for non-model fungi and rare edible and medicinal mushrooms. The CDDP method has been successfully used as a biodiversity tool, strain identification, and breeding in mycology (Golian *et al.*, 2022a). For instance, Golian *et al.* (2022a) were CDDP markers that distinguished between wild and cultivated strains of *Pleurotus ostreatus*, a species that displays exceptionally high genetic diversity that could be used for breeding and conservation. Moreover, CDDP markers have been applied for the study of genetic diversity and population structure of a variety of different mushroom species, and some genetic diversity was observed in *G. lucidum* from a range of ecological species (Pawlik *et al.*, 2015).

Start codon targeted (SCoT) markers are sequence related markers developed on the short-conserved regions around the translation initiation codon ATG in plant and fungal genomes. In fungi, particularly in mushrooms, the SCoT markers use the evolutionary conservation of coding sequence

flanks to amplify gene-rich fraction of the genome (Rai, 2023). These individual primers of ≈ 18 bp in length do not require prior genomic information and can be applied to any non-model mushroom species. In fungi SCoT markers have been properly used for different applications such as determination of genetic diversity, identity of cultivars, study of population structure and in some cases for phylogeny. For instance, in *Pleurotus eryngii*, SCoT markers have shown their efficiency to detect the genetic differences of isolates from various ecological niches (Zhao *et al.*, 2013).

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials

3.1.1 Mushroom materials

In February 2024, at the end of winter, we collected sixty-two samples of wild mushrooms from eight different sites in the Kurdistan area of Iraq (Fig. 3.1). The distance between the sampling areas ranged from eighty to two hundred kilometers. To avoid duplication of identical genotypes during sampling, we obtained each isolate at a minimum distance of one km from each other. For each geographical population, (Table 3.1) displays the sample size along with their names, strains, accessions numbers, and altitudes. During sampling, the samples were maintained in the bag and placed in the chilled box. Afterwards, they were stored at 4 C in the laboratory.

Figure 3. 1 A map depicting the locations where distinct mushroom strains are harvested.

Table 3. 1 Name, strains, accessions number, and altitudes of different mushroom samples collected from different locations.

Code	Identified sample	Strain	Location of sampling	Altitude (m)	Accession number	
S1	<i>Agrocybe aegerita</i>	AgA-QAL-1	Qaladiza	586	PQ679358	
S2	<i>Agrocybe dura</i>	AgD-QAL-2	Qaladiza		PQ680084	
S3	<i>Agrocybe dura</i>	AgD-QAL-3	Qaladiza		PQ680083	
S4	<i>Agrocybe aegerita</i>	AgA-QAL-4	Qaladiza		PQ680085	
S5	<i>Agaricus campestris</i>	AgC-QAL-5	Qaladiza		PQ679044	
S6	<i>Agrocybe dura</i>	AgD-QAL-6	Qaladiza		PQ679043	
S7	<i>Agaricus campestris</i>	AgA-QAL-7	Qaladiza		PQ679045	
S8	<i>Agaricus campestris</i>	AgA-QAL-8	Qaladiza		PQ679046	
S9	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-PEN-9	Penjwen	1272	PQ680647	
S10	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-PEN-10	Penjwen		PQ680646	
S11	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-PEN-11	Penjwen		PQ680649	
S12	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-PEN-12	Penjwen		PQ680655	
S13	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-PEN-13	Penjwen		PQ680656	
S14	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-PEN-15	Penjwen		PQ680668	
S15	<i>Amanita crocea</i>	AmC-DUK-17	Dukan	798	PQ686237	
S16	<i>Amanita crocea</i>	AmC-DUK-18	Dukan		PQ686016	
S17	<i>Amanita lividopallescens</i>	AmL-DUK-19	Dukan		PQ685979	
S18	<i>Amanita lividopallescens</i>	AmL-DUK-20	Dukan		PQ681289	
S19	<i>Amanita crocea</i>	AmC-DUK-21	Dukan		PQ681290	
S20	<i>Pleurotus eryngii</i>	PIE-DUK-22	Dukan		PQ681292	
S21	<i>Pleurotus eryngii</i>	PIE-DUK-23	Dukan		PQ685981	
S22	<i>Pleurotus eryngii</i>	PIE-DUK-24	Dukan		PQ681296	
S23	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-BAS-25	Basneh	1573	PQ682616	
S24	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-BAS-26	Basneh		PQ682630	
S25	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-BAS-27	Basneh		PQ682658	
S26	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-BAS-28	Basneh		PQ682661	
S27	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-BAS-29	Basneh		PQ682665	
S28	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-BAS-30	Basneh		PQ682666	
S29	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-BAS-31	Basneh		PQ683183	
S30	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-BAS-32	Basneh		PQ685808	
S31	<i>Amanita crocea</i>	AmC-ZEW-33	Zewe		1583	PQ686266
S32	<i>Amanita lividopallescens</i>	AmL-ZEW-34	Zewe			PQ686317
S33	<i>Amanita lividopallescens</i>	AmL-ZEW-35	Zewe	PQ686318		
S34	<i>Amanita crocea</i>	AmC-ZEW-36	Zewe	PQ686633		
S35	<i>Amanita crocea</i>	AmC-ZEW-37	Zewe	PQ686958		
S36	<i>Amanita crocea</i>	AmC-ZEW-38	Zewe	PQ686964		
S37	<i>Pleurotus columbinus</i>	PIC-ZEW-39	Zewe	PQ686965		
S38	<i>Pleurotus columbinus</i>	PIC-ZEW-40	Zewe	PQ687023		
S39	<i>Agaricus pseudolutosus</i>	AgaP-RAN-41	Ranya	882	PQ720781	
S40	<i>Agaricus pseudolutosus</i>	AgaP-RAN-42	Ranya		PQ720782	
S41	<i>Agaricus pseudolutosus</i>	AgaP-RAN-43	Ranya		PQ722530	
S42	<i>Agaricus pseudolutosus</i>	AgaP-RAN-44	Ranya		PQ722533	
S43	<i>Amanita vittadinii</i>	AmV-RAN-45	Ranya		PQ720786	
S44	<i>Amanita vittadinii</i>	AmV-RAN-46	Ranya		PQ720789	
S45	<i>Amanita vittadinii</i>	AmV-RAN-47	Ranya		PQ720788	
S46	<i>Agaricus pseudolutosus</i>	AgaP-RAN-48	Ranya		PQ722534	
S47	<i>Amanita crocea</i>	AmC-QAR-49	Qaradagh	1708	PQ720780	
S48	<i>Amanita lividopallescens</i>	AmL-QAR-50	Qaradagh		PQ720981	
S49	<i>Amanita lividopallescens</i>	AmL-QAR-51	Qaradagh		PQ721015	
S50	<i>Amanita lividopallescens</i>	AmL-QAR-52	Qaradagh		PQ721021	
S51	<i>Amanita lividopallescens</i>	AmL-QAR-53	Qaradagh		PQ721023	
S52	<i>Amanita crocea</i>	AmC-QAR-54	Qaradagh		PQ721027	
S53	<i>Amanita vittadinii</i>	AmV-QAR-55	Qaradagh		PQ722535	
S54	<i>Amanita vittadinii</i>	AmV-QAR-56	Qaradagh		PQ721036	
S55	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-QAR-57	Qaradagh		PQ721038	
S56	<i>Amanita vittadinii</i>	AmV-HAL-58	Halabja		900	PQ721310
S57	<i>Amanita vittadinii</i>	AmV-HAL-59	Halabja	PQ721312		
S58	<i>Amanita vittadinii</i>	AmV-HAL-60	Halabja	PQ721315		
S59	<i>Amanita vittadinii</i>	AmV-HAL-61	Halabja	PQ721317		
S60	<i>Amanita vittadinii</i>	AmV-HAL-62	Halabja	PQ721318		
S61	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-HAL-63	Halabja	PQ721319		
S62	<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	AgaL-HAL-64	Halabja	PQ721320		
S63	<i>Agaricus bisporus</i>	AgaB-SC-65	Sulaimani Center	882		PQ895553

Figure 3. 2 Fruiting bodies of 11 mushroom species were collected from different regions.

3.1.2. Chemical materials

1. Methanol (Biochem, France)
2. Ethanol (Biochem, France)
3. Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (Sigma, Germany)
4. Sodium carbonate ((Biochem, France)
5. Gallic acid (Sigma, Germany)
6. Quercetin (Sigma, Germany)
7. Aluminium chloride (Biochem, France)
8. Potassium acetate (Biochem, France)
9. 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (Sigma, Germany)
10. 6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman-2-carboxylic acid (Trolox) (Sigma, Germany)

11. Anthrone powder (Biochem, France)
12. Sulfuric acid (Biochem, France)
13. Glucose ((Biochem, France)
14. Sodium hydroxide (Biochem, France)
15. Copper sulfate (CuSO₄) (Biochem, France)
16. Potassium sodium tartrate (Biochem, France)
17. Bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Biochem, France)
18. Tris-hydroxymethyl-aminomethane (Biochem, France)
19. ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (Biochem, France)
20. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (Biochem, France)
21. Sodium dodecyl sulfate (Biochem, France)
22. Guanidine thiocyanate (Biochem, France)
23. Sodium chloride (Biochem, France)
24. Glacial acetic acid (Biochem, France)
25. Hydrochloric acid (Biochem, France)
26. DNA purification kit (AddBio, Daejeon, Republic of Korea)
27. Agarose (Biochem, France)
28. Ethidium bromide (Biochem, France)

Equipment used:

1. Prime Thermal Cycler (PCR), Bibby Scientific Ltd ,UK
2. Water Bath, Daihan Labtech Co., Ltd. ,Korea
3. Drying Oven, Memmert GmbH + Co. KG ,Germany
4. Shaking Incubator / Orbital Shaker /Laboratory Shaker, Eppendorf, Germany
5. Microwave Appliance, Kenwood ,China
6. Sensitive Balance, Adam Equipment ,UK
7. Centrifuge, Labnet International ,USA
8. Gel Electrophoresis System, Cleaver Scientific Ltd ,UK

3.2 Methods**3.2.1 Morphological features of the mushrooms**

Mushroom morphological traits were determined by measuring the fresh weight (g), stem length (cm), vertical diameter of pileus (cm), and horizontal diameter of pileus (cm). Moisture (%), and dry matter contents (%) were calculated by oven drying to constant weight (AOAC, 2016). To determine the percentage of dry matter (DM) in the fresh fruiting body, a 10 g sample was prepared by chopping

it into smaller pieces. The samples were kept in an electric oven and dried to a constant weight at 55 ± 1 °C (Tahir *et al.*, 2023; Tahir *et al.*, 2022). Three replicates were used for each sample. DM percentage was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Dry matter (\%)} = \frac{\text{Dry weight}}{\text{Fresh weight}} \times 100$$

After calculating the DM of the different samples, the moisture content (MC) was computed with three replications using the following equation:

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Fresh weight} - \text{Dry weight})}{\text{Fresh weight}} \times 100$$

3.2.2 DNA extraction

The cap mushroom of samples (0.5 g) was ground using nitrogen liquid. The DNA was extracted using the procedure described by Ahmed *et al.* (2023). The purity of genomic DNA was checked using gel electrophoresis on a 1.1% agarose gel (Addbio, Korea), and the quality was determined using Nanodrop spectrophotometry (NanoPLUS, MAALANLAB, Sweden). The DNA sample was maintained at a temperature of -17°C.

DNA extraction protocol

1. To initiate cell lysis, lysis buffer about 900–1000 μL was added to the washed plant material along with 10 μL of RNase.
2. All tubes were precisely incubated at 65 °C approximately 70 minutes and also during the incubation samples gently inverted every 10 minutes.
3. Subsequently, potassium acetate (5M) which had (pH 6.5) in amount of 230 μL was added and mixed thoroughly, then all tubes were refrigerated about eight minutes.
4. Next, all samples were centrifuged completely at 12,000–16,000 rpm about 17 minutes.
5. The resulting supernatants were transferred into sterile 2 mL microcentrifuge tubes, and 800 μL of chloroform was added for each tube.
6. Tubes were inverted gently to ensure proper mixing of the solution.
7. The samples were centrifuged for another time at 12,000–16,000 rpm for 17 minutes.
8. The phase layer on the top was cautiously transferred into a sterile Eppendorf tube (2 mL).
9. One mL of Buffer AW1 was added to the solution and mixed perfectly.
10. The centrifuge set up at 8000 rpm for 4 minutes to centrifuge the spin column.
11. The flow solution was discarded.
12. AW2 washing buffer (500 μL) was loaded to a new spin column.
13. The spin column put in centrifuge at 8000 rpm for 4 minutes was centrifuged.

14. Then the flow through discarded again.
15. A second wash was performed using an additional 500 μ L of washing buffer AW2.
16. The spin column put into the centrifuge at 8000 rpm for another 4 minutes.
17. The removal of flow solution was done.
18. The spin column was centrifuged at maximum speed (12,000–16,000 rpm) for at least 5 minutes to dry completely.
19. The spin columns were taken to new sterile 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes.
20. A volume of 110 μ L of elution buffer was applied to each column and then the tubes incubated at room temperature about 5 minutes.
21. Finally, the collection tube was used for having eluted DNA by using centrifuge at 7000 rpm for 4 minutes

3.2.3 Polymerase chain reaction, purification, and DNA sequencing

The complete ITS1-5.8S-ITS2 region (Table 3.2) was amplified using PCR using a master mix kit (AddBio, Daejeon, Republic of Korea) in accordance with manufacturer protocols. The ITS primers, PCR circumstances, DNA separation, and DNA purification from agarose gel were detailed in our published article by Khal *et al.*, (2023) . According to Khal (2023), PCR amplification of the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region using ITS1 (5' TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG 3') and ITS4 (5' TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC 3') primers has proven effective for fungal DNA characterization. In this study, amplification was performed in a 26 μ L reaction mixture containing 5 μ L of genomic DNA, 10 μ L of AddStart Taq Master Mix (Addbio, Daejeon, Republic of Korea), 2 μ L of each primer (10 μ M), and 7 μ L of deionized water. The thermal cycling conditions within an initial denaturation at 94 °C for 10 minutes, next 35 cycles of denaturation at 94 °C for 1 minute, annealing at 55 °C for 1 minute, and extension at 72 °C for 2 minutes, concluding with a final extension at 72 °C for 10 minutes. A negative control without DNA was used in each PCR run to ensure specificity. PCR products were resolved on a 1.5% agarose gel using 1X TBE buffer, stained with ethidium bromide, and visualized under UV illumination. DNA bands corresponding to the ITS region were excised and purified using a Gel Extraction Kit (Addbio, Korea), and sequencing was conducted by Macrogen (South Korea). The resulting sequences were then compared with existing entries in the NCBI database.

Table 3. 2 Sequences and annealing temperatures of ITS gene, CDDP and SCoT markers.

Primers	Sequence (5' to 3')	Annealing temperature (°C)	Reference
---------	---------------------	----------------------------	-----------

ITS gene			
ITS 1	TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG	55	(Khal et al., 2023)
ITS 4	TCCTCCGCTTA TTGATATGC	55	
CDDP markers			
KNOX2	CACTGGTGGGAGCTSCAC	50	(Collard & Mackill, 2009; Rasul, Grundler, & Abdul-razzak Tahir, 2022)
WRKYF1	TGGCGSAAGTACGGCCAG	50	
WRKY-R3	GCASGTGTGCTCGCC	50	
KNOX1	AAGGSAAGCTSCCSAAG	50	
ERF2	GCSGAGATCCGSGACCC	50	
MYB1	GGCAAGGGCTGCCGC	50	
ERF1	CACTACCCCGGSCTSCG	50	
WRKY-R3B	CCGCTCGTGTGSACG	50	
MYB2	GGCAAGGGCTGCCGC	50	
WRKY-R2B	TGSTGSATGCTCCCG	50	
ABP1-1	ACSCCSATCCACCGC	50	
MADS-1	ATGGGCCGSGGCAAGGTGC	50	
SCoT markers			
SCoT3	CAACAATGGCTACCACCG	51.27	(Ahmed, Tahir, Salih, & Talebi, 2021; Collard & Mackill, 2009; Majeed, Faraj, Rasul, Lateef, & Tahir, 2024a; Rasul et al., 2022)
SCoT12	ACGACATGGCGACCAACG	55.93	
SCoT13	ACGACATGGCGACCATCG	55.39	
SCoT14	ACGACATGGCGACCACGC	58.6	
SCoT15	ACGACATGGCGACCGCGA	59.9	
SCoT19	ACCATGGCTACCACCGGC	57.1	
SCoT20	ACCATGGCTACCACCGCG	57.5	
SCoT21	ACGACATGGCGACCCACA	56.7	
SCoT23	CACCATGGCTACCACCAG	52.43	
SCoT24	CACCATGGCTACCACCAT	51.6	
SCoT34	ACCATGGCTACCACCGCA	56.3	
SCoT35	CATGGCTACCACCGGCC	57.9	

3.2.4 Genetic diversity analysis

Two molecular techniques, SCoT (Start codon-targeting) and CDDP (Conserved DNA-derived polymorphism) markers, were employed to assess the genetic diversity among various samples. A total of 24 different markers were used in the PCR method for SCoT and CDDP, comprising 12 primers for each marker type (Table 3.2) (Collard & Mackill, 2009; Majeed *et al.*, 2024b; Rasul *et al.*, 2024) To assess genetic variation among fungal samples, a total of 12 SCoT and 12 CDDP primers were used. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification was performed in a total reaction volume of 25 μ L, consisting of 5 μ L of genomic DNA template, 10 μ L of AddStart Taq Master Mix (Addbio, Korea), 5 μ L of primer, and 5 μ L of distilled water. The reactions were performed in a thermal cycler (Applied Biosystems, USA) under the following conditions: initial denaturation at 94°C for 9 minutes, then 36 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 1 minute applied, annealing at primer-specific temperature (50–60°C) for 1 minute, and extension at 72°C for 2 minutes. A final extension step was

performed at 72°C for 8 minutes. Amplified PCR products were separated on 1.8% agarose gels stained with ethidium bromide and visualized under UV illumination.

3.2.5 Biochemical measurement

Diverse biochemical parameters were evaluated, using 0.10 g of freshly ground material from each mushroom species. The tissue samples were incubated with 1 mL of 80% methanol solution overnight and subsequently centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant obtained after centrifugation was used for biochemical analyses. These biochemical parameters included total phenolic content, TPC (μg gallic acid/g tissue fresh weight), total flavonoid content, TFC (μg quercetin/g tissue fresh weight), antioxidant activity, 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (μg trolox/g tissue fresh weight), and soluble sugar content, SSC (μg glucose/g tissue fresh weight). The methodologies for such biochemical assessments have been outlined in our previous study (Ahmad *et al.*, 2020; Lateef *et al.*, 2021; Tahir *et al.*, 2024; Tahir *et al.*, 2023). To determine the protein (PC) relative to the fresh weight of the tissue, a fresh powdered sample (0.5 g) was prepared and mixed with 10 mL of 0.01N NaOH, followed by 20 min incubation in an ice bath. The samples were then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 15 min at 4 °C. PC was quantified using the Lowry method (Walker, 1984; Waterborg and Matthews, 1984). For each measurement, three replicates were used per sample.

3.2.5.1 Total phenolic content (TPC)

The determination of total phenolic content (TPC) in fresh mushroom tissue followed the method outlined by Tahir *et al.* (2023), with minor adjustments. It is summarized as a following: 0.1 g of finely pulverized mushroom tissue was blended with 1000 μL of 80% methanol and shaken for 40 min. The mixture was subsequently stored at 5 °C overnight to facilitate extraction. After incubation, A centrifuge was used to spin the samples at 12,000 rpm over a 10 mins interval, and the transparent supernatant was carefully retrieved for further analysis. To quantify TPC, a volume of 100 μL of the extract was mixed with 1050 μL of Folin–Ciocalteu reagent diluted 1:9 with distilled water. After a 7-minute reaction period, 850 μL of sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) at a concentration of %10 was added, the mixture was incubated under dark condition for a period of 30 minutes at room temperature. A change in solution color to light blue indicated the presence of phenolics. Absorbance was then measured at 750 nm utilizing a UV-visible spectrophotometer (UVM6100, MAANLAB AB, Sweden), with the reagent mixture used as a blank. Gallic acid (GAE) served as the standard phenolic compound. The standard curve was obtained by dissolving 9 mg of gallic acid in 9 mL of methanol (1 mg/mL), followed by serial dilutions of 0-25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. A linear correlation between absorbance and gallic acid concentration at 750 nm was established. Phenolic content was quantified

using a gallic acid standard curve (Fig 3.3). The calculation of TPC was by using the following equation:

$$\text{TPC } (\mu\text{g GAE/g FW}) = \frac{V}{W} \times C$$

Where: V refers the extract volume (mL), W is the sample fresh weight (g), and C is the gallic acid concentration which is determined from the standard curve.

Figure 3. 3 Gallic acid standard curve.

3.2.5.2 Total flavonoid content (TFC)

The determination of total flavonoid content (TFC) in fresh mushroom tissue was examined by using the aluminum chloride colorimetric method. Nearly 0.1 g of ground sample was extracted in 1 mL of 80% methanol by well shaking for 40 minutes, followed by overnight incubation at 5 °C. Then the extract was centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 10 minutes, and the supernatant was kept for doing more examination for further analysis. The solution of quercetin standard (1 mg/mL) was prepared by melting 8 mg of quercetin in 8 mL of methanol, and serial dilutions (0–80 µg/mL) were used to obtain a standard curve. For entire samples, 250 µL of the extract was mixed with 0.90 mL of 80% methanol, 0.30 mL of 2% aluminum chloride, 0.08 mL of 1 M potassium acetate, and 1.72 mL of distilled water. After 30 minutes of incubation at room temperature, absorbance was measured at 415 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (UV-365, SHIMADZU, Japan). TFC was calculated based on the quercetin standard curve and expressed as micrograms of quercetin equivalent per gram of fresh weight (Fig 3.4) using the formula:

$$\text{TFC } (\mu\text{g QR/g FW}) = \frac{V}{W} \times C$$

Where V is the extract volume (mL), W is the sample fresh weight (g), and C is the quercetin concentration derived from the standard curve.

Figure 3. 4 Curve of quercetin standard calibration.

3.2.5.3 Antioxidant capacity (AC)

The antioxidant activity of mushroom samples was assessed by using the DPPH (1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging assay. Around 0.1 g of finely ground fresh mushroom tissue was taken with 1 mL of 80% methanol. The mixture was shaken well approximately forty minutes and then incubated at 5 °C overnight. After incubation, the samples were centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 10 minutes, and the clear supernatant was used for analysis. A volume of 40 µL of the extract was added to 2 mL of freshly prepared DPPH solution (0.0038 g DPPH in 100 mL of 95% methanol). The reaction mixtures remained in the dark at room temperature for 30 minutes. Absorbance was measured at 517 nm UV-visible spectrophotometer (UVM6100, MAANLAB AB, Sweden) was used against a blank consisting of 95% methanol. To construct the standard curve, Trolox was used as a reference antioxidant (Fig 3.5). A stock solution of Trolox was prepared by dissolving 12 mg in 12 mL of 75% ethanol. From this, serial dilutions were made to produce concentrations of 0-40 µg/mL. A linear relationship between absorbance and Trolox concentration was observed. Antioxidant capacity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Antioxidant capacity by DPPH } (\mu\text{g Trolox/g FW}) = \frac{V}{W} \times C$$

Where V is the extract volume (mL), W is the fresh weight of the sample (g), and C is the Trolox concentration obtained from the standard curve.

Figure 3. 5 Trolox standard calibration curve.

3.2.5.4 Sugar soluble content (SSC)

Briefly, 0.1 g of finely ground fresh mushroom tissue was mixed with 1000 µL of distilled water and shaken for 20 minutes. The mixture was then boiled at 92 °C for 30 minutes and subsequently cooled using cold water. Following this, the samples were centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 12 minutes, and the resulting supernatant was collected for further analysis. The anthrone reagent was prepared by dissolving 0.15 g of anthrone in 16 mL of distilled water, followed by the addition of 84 mL of sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) with continuous shaking until the solution was fully homogenized. For the assay, 25 µL of the collected supernatant was mixed with 2000 µL of the prepared anthrone reagent. This mixture was incubated at 92 °C for 6 minutes, during which the solution color shifted to dark green. After cooling to room temperature, absorbance was measured at 620 nm against the reagent blank using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (UVM6100, MAANLAB AB, Sweden). A glucose stock solution as a following: dissolving 10 mg of glucose in 10 mL of deionized water to obtain a 1 mg/mL concentration. Numbers of dilutions were prepared (0-80 µg/mL) to generate a standard curve (Fig 3.6). A linear relationship was observed between the absorbance at 620 nm and glucose concentrations. The calculation of soluble sugar content (SSC) was by the following formula:

$$SSC \left(\frac{\mu\text{g}}{\text{g FW}} \right) = \frac{V}{W} \times C$$

Where V is extracting volume (mL), W is mushroom sample fresh weight (g), and C is the concentration of glucose taken from the standard curve.

Figure 3. 6 Standard curve of glucose.

3.2.5.5 Protein content (PC)

Protein content was assessed through the use of 0.5 g of freshly pulverized mushroom, a volume of 1600 µL of 0.01N sodium hydroxide was introduced, shaking for 20 minutes and incubating in the ice for 20 minutes. Centrifugation was done for all the samples for 15 minutes at 10000 rpm in 4°C, then the collection of supernatants was taken place, and it was stored at 4° C. The first reagent (alkaline copper) solution was prepared by mixing 350 ml (2% sodium carbonate) with 7 mL of 0.5% copper sulphate, which dissolved in 1% potassium sodium tartrate. The second reagent (Folin–Ciocalteu) was prepared by mixing 1 volume of Folin–Ciocalteu reagent with 1 volume of 0.1 N sodium hydroxide (v/v). The procedure involved mixing 1500 µL of the supernatant with 5 mL of first reagent followed by 0.5 mL the second reagent, respectively. Sample absorbance was recorded at 660 nm relative to blank solution using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (UVM6100, MAANLAB AB, Sweden). For creating the standard curve, fifty mg of bovine serum albumin (BSA) dissolved in 50 mL of distilled water in a volumetric flask in order to prepare the standard curve. Distilled water (30 mL) was added to (20 mL) of the solution and mixed thoroughly. One mL of this solution contains 400 µg protein. A series (1 mL) of dilutions of BSA (0, 40, 80, 120, 160, 200, 240, 280, 320, 400 µg) was prepared and mixed separately with both reagents 5 mL alkaline copper and 0.5 mL Folin–Ciocalteu (Fig 3.7). Between the absorbance values Linear regression was examined at 660 nm and the protein concentrations (Lowry *et al.*, 1951).

Figure 3. 7 Standard curve of bovine serum albumin.

3.2.6 Statistical data analysis

3.2.6.1 Molecular analysis

To ensure the highest quality of sequences, we implemented chromatograms of sequencing in the SnapGene version 3.1 software to verify the sequences and replicate them as necessary. The sequences were aligned using the Clustal W utility in Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis 11 (MEGA 11). A phylogenetic tree was constructed with 1000 bootstrap replicates using the neighbor-joining tree technique to establish pretrial reliability. The detectable PCR products produced with SCoT and CDDP were subjected to an analysis. We only considered strong, distinct, and repetitive bands to decrease the chance of inaccuracy. We utilized numbers 1 and 0 to indicate the presence and absence of amplified bands, respectively, in order to generate a binary matrix for each sample. The radar chart was generated by XLSTAT version 2020.1.3. Principal component analysis and cluster analysis were conducted using the Ward method to generate the cluster diagram with JMP version 18. Using GenAIEx version 6.51b2, genetic distance, diversity indices, and analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) were calculated. The polymorphism information content (PIC) was calculated using the formula outlined by Aziz and Tahir (2023).

3.2.6.2 Morpho-chemical analysis

Significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$ and $p \leq 0.01$) among mushroom species were analyzed by one-way ANOVA with randomized complete block design (RCBD) and Duncan's new multiple range tests

using the XLSTAT software version 2022.3.1 (Addinsoft, New York, NY, USA). Multivariate and correlation analysis were performed using JMP software version 18 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA). XLSTAT software version 2022.3.1 was used to generate the bar and radar charts.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

4.1.1 Molecular analysis of mushroom samples

4.1.1.1 Identification and phylogenetic analysis of mushroom specimens

The BLASTn of ITS sequences was carried out using NCBI blast tool. Results identified seventeen *Agaricus litoralis*, two *Pleurotus columbinus*, three *Pleurotus eryngii*, three *Agrocybe dura*, eight *Amanita lividopallescens*, nine *Amanita crocea*, ten *Amanita vittadinii*, five *Agaricus pseudolutosus*, three *Agaricus campestris*, two *Agrocybe aegerita*, and one *Agaricus bisporus* (Fig. 4.1).

Figure 4. 1 Number of identified strains in a collection of 63 samples through the ITS nuclear gene.

Phylogenetic analysis showed that there were two main groups of 63 isolates (Fig. 4.2A). Five different strains of *Pleurotus columbinus* and *Pleurotus eryngii*, which belong to the genus *Pleurotus*, made up the first group (green line). In the second set of 58 isolates (red line), nine species were represented across three genera: *Agaricus litoralis*, *Agrocybe dura*, *Amanita lividopallescens*, *Amanita crocea*, *Amanita vittadinii*, *A. pseudolutosus*, *Agaricus campestris*, *Agrocybe aegerita*, and *Agaricus bisporus*. After strain identification, the dendrogram (Fig. 4.2B) divided the eleven species into three distinct categories based on the frequency of the nucleotides A, T, C, and G. *Agaricus bisporus*, *Agaricus litoralis*, *Agaricus pseudolutosus*, and *Agrocybe aegerita* formed the initial group of taxa (red line). *Amanita vittadinii*, *Amanita crocea*, and *Amanita lividopallescens* were the members of the genus *Amanita*, forming the second clade (green line), while *Pleurotus columbinus*, *Pleurotus eryngii*, *Agrocybe dura*, and *Agaricus campestris* were the members of the third clade (blue line). The four genera were categorized into two groups based on the frequency of four nucleotides. The first group consisted of three genera: *Agaricus*, *Agrocybe*, and *Amanita*; the second group was

created by the genus *Pleurotus* (Fig. 4.2C). As seen in Figure 4.3, the range of C+G frequencies was 0.43 to 0.50, whereas A+T frequencies were 0.50 to 0.57. The highest and lowest A+T and G+C frequencies were found in *Amanita* genus.

Figure 4. 2 Clustering of mushroom specimens based on ITS gene sequencing data. A. Consolidation of all isolated samples. B. Classification of various mushroom species according to the prevalence of adenine, cytosine, guanine, and thymine. C. Clustering of different genus.

Figure 4. 3 Illustrating the GC and AT contents in various species (A) and genera (B) of both wild and cultivated mushrooms.

4.1.1.2 Marker information and genetic diversity of CDDP and SCoT methods acquired from mushroom samples

Using 12 polymorphic CDDP primers, the present investigation produced 204 markers from 63 samples, covering 11 species across 4 genera of mushrooms. From 14 (MYB1) to 18 (WRKY-R3, ERF2, MYB1, ERF1, WRKY-R2B, and ABP1-1) polymorphic fragments were found. The PIC had a mean of 0.39 and a range of 0.35 to 0.43 (WRKY-R2B to ERF1), as shown in Figure 4.4 and Appendix 1 and 2. Concerning SCoT markers (Fig.4.5), the number of polymorphic bands varied from 11 (SCoT23) to 18 (SCoT21), while the PIC ranged from 0.35 (SCoT35) to 0.44 (SCoT20).

Figure 4. 4 Number of polymorphic bands (A) and polymorphism information content (B) for various CDDP markers gathered from different species and genera of 63 mushroom samples.

Figure 4. 5 Polymorphic bands number (A) and polymorphism information content (B) from varies SCoT markers from 63 mushroom samples of different species and genera.

Species genetic diversity indicators, as determined by CDDP markers, are presented in Table 4.1. The number of different alleles (N_a), number of effective alleles (N_e), Shannons' information index (I), expected heterozygosity (H_e), and unbiased expected heterozygosity (uH_e) varied from 1.01 (WRKY-R3) to 1.24 (ERF1), 1.23 (MADS-1) to 1.33 (MYB1), 0.21 (MADS-1) to 0.29 (MYB1), 0.14 (MADS-1) to 0.19 (MYB1), and 0.15 (MADS-1 and KNOX1) to 0.22 (MYB1 and KNOX1), respectively. The N_a , N_e , I , H_e , and uH_e genetic diversity indices of the genera were as follows: 1.49 (WRKY-R3B) and 1.78 (KNOX1), 1.33 (WRKY-R2B) and 1.51 (ERF1), 0.33 (WRKY-R2B) and 0.44 (ERF1), 0.21 (WRKY-R2B) and 0.30 (ERF1), and 0.22 (WRKY-R2B), and 0.31 (ERF1), respectively. The genetic diversity indicators of species and genera, as determined by SCoT markers, are summarized in Table 4.1. N_a , N_e , I , H_e , and uH_e genetic diversity indices of the species differed from 0.98 (SCoT35) to 1.31 (SCoT20), 1.24 (SCoT35) to 1.35 (SCoT20), 0.22 (SCoT35) to 0.32 (SCoT15), 0.15 (SCoT35) to 0.21 (SCoT15), and 0.17 (SCoT35) to 0.24 (SCoT15), respectively. The N_a , N_e , I , H_e , and uH_e genetic diversity indices of the genera were 1.38% (SCoT24) and 1.77

(SCoT13), 1.31 (SCoT35) and 1.52 (SCoT20), 0.30 (SCoT35) and 0.46 (SCoT20), 0.19 (SCoT35) and 0.31 (SCoT20), and 0.20 (SCoT35) and 0.33 (SCoT20), respectively.

Table 4. 1 Genetic diversity indices of several markers of CDDP and SCoT derived from different genera and species of 63 mushroom samples.

CDDP markers	Species					Genus				
	Na	Ne	I	He	uHe	Na	Ne	I	He	uHe
KNOX2	1.08	1.29	0.26	0.17	0.20	1.59	1.39	0.38	0.24	0.26
WRKYF1	1.15	1.30	0.27	0.18	0.20	1.50	1.37	0.35	0.23	0.24
WRKY-R3	1.01	1.24	0.22	0.14	0.16	1.54	1.39	0.37	0.24	0.25
KNOX1	1.21	1.31	0.28	0.19	0.22	1.78	1.40	0.40	0.25	0.27
ERF2	1.17	1.31	0.27	0.18	0.21	1.61	1.42	0.38	0.25	0.27
MYB1	1.23	1.33	0.29	0.19	0.22	1.63	1.48	0.41	0.28	0.29
ERF1	1.24	1.31	0.28	0.18	0.21	1.71	1.51	0.44	0.30	0.31
WRKY-R3B	1.10	1.26	0.23	0.15	0.17	1.49	1.40	0.36	0.24	0.25
MYB2	1.08	1.27	0.25	0.16	0.18	1.50	1.37	0.36	0.23	0.24
WRKY-R2B	1.10	1.26	0.24	0.16	0.17	1.53	1.33	0.33	0.21	0.22
ABP1-1	1.16	1.32	0.27	0.18	0.21	1.56	1.47	0.40	0.27	0.29
MADS-1	1.04	1.23	0.21	0.14	0.15	1.56	1.40	0.37	0.24	0.26
Mean	1.13	1.28	0.25	0.17	0.19	1.58	1.41	0.38	0.25	0.26
SCoT markers	Species					Genus				
SCoT3	1.23	1.32	0.28	0.19	0.21	1.61	1.46	0.41	0.27	0.29
SCoT12	1.27	1.30	0.27	0.18	0.20	1.71	1.45	0.41	0.27	0.29
SCoT13	1.15	1.31	0.27	0.18	0.21	1.77	1.44	0.42	0.27	0.29
SCoT14	1.14	1.31	0.28	0.18	0.21	1.58	1.39	0.37	0.24	0.25
SCoT15	1.35	1.34	0.32	0.21	0.24	1.75	1.43	0.42	0.27	0.29
SCoT19	1.14	1.32	0.28	0.19	0.21	1.57	1.43	0.39	0.26	0.27
SCoT20	1.31	1.35	0.31	0.21	0.23	1.71	1.52	0.46	0.31	0.33
SCoT21	1.03	1.26	0.23	0.15	0.17	1.46	1.37	0.34	0.22	0.23
SCoT23	1.08	1.29	0.24	0.16	0.18	1.55	1.45	0.40	0.27	0.28
SCoT24	1.11	1.27	0.25	0.16	0.18	1.38	1.33	0.31	0.20	0.21
SCoT34	1.19	1.34	0.29	0.20	0.23	1.58	1.41	0.38	0.25	0.26
SCoT35	0.98	1.24	0.22	0.15	0.17	1.40	1.31	0.30	0.19	0.20
Mean	1.17	1.30	0.27	0.18	0.20	1.59	1.42	0.38	0.25	0.27

Na: number of observed alleles, Ne: effective number of alleles, He: expected heterozygosity or gene diversity, I: Shannon's information index, and uHe: unbiased expected heterozygosity

4.1.1.3 Genetic diversity parameters among different populations (species and genera) of mushroom strains

Gene diversity indicators at the population level (species and genera) exhibited variation among mushroom strains, as detailed in Tables 4.2 and 4.3. According to CDDP data, the average proportion of polymorphic loci (PPL) was 48.53% across 11 species and 75.98% across 4 genera, with species ranging from 0.00% (*Agaricus bisporus*) to 91.18% (*Agaricus litoralis*) and genera ranging from 52.45% (*Agrocybe*) to 94.61% (*Agaricus*). The genetic diversity indices Na, Ne, I, He, and uHe for the species measured varied from 0.45 (*Agrocybe aegerita*) to 1.82 (*Agaricus litoralis*), 1.04 (*Aegerita aegerita*) to 1.47 (*Agaricus litoralis*), 0.00 (*Agaricus bisporus*) to 0.43 (*Agaricus litoralis*), 0.00 (*Agaricus bisporus*) to 0.28 (*Agaricus litoralis*), and 0.00 (*Agaricus bisporus*) to 0.30 (*Agaricus*

litoralis), respectively. The measured genera' genetic diversity indices were 1.40 (*Pleurotus*) to 1.89 (*Agaricus*), 1.29 (*Agrocybe*) to 1.49 (*Amanita*), 0.27 (*Agrocybe*) to 0.46 (*Amanita*), 0.17 (*Agrocybe*) to 0.30 (*Amanita*), and 0.19 (*Agrocybe*) to 0.31 (*Amanita*), respectively. The average number of private bands across all species was 0.36, ranging from 1 (*Agrocybe dura*) to 2 (*Agaricus litoralis*), but the average number of private bands across all genera was 2.75, with a range from 1 (*Agrocybe* and *Pleurotus*) to 5 (*Agaricus*).

Based on the SCoT data, the maximum Na, Ne, I, He, and uHe of 1.75, 1.43, 0.41, 0.27, 0.28, and 87.57 were recorded with *Agaricus litoralis*, respectively. The highest PPL of 87.57% was seen with *Agaricus litoralis*. The average number of private bands across all species was 0.36, ranging from 1 (*Agaricus litoralis*) to 3 (*Amanita vittadinii*). At the genus level, the greatest values for Na, Ne, I, He, uHe, and PPL were 1.90, 1.48, 0.46, 0.30, 0.30, and 94.67% for the genus *Amanita*. A wide range of 2 to 5 specific bands appeared across all genera.

Table 4. 2 Genetic diversity indices of various species and genera identified in a collection of 63 mushrooms based on CDDP data.

Species	Species						
	Na	Ne	I	He	uHe	PPL	PB
<i>A. campestris</i>	1.01	1.27	0.23	0.16	0.19	42.16	0.00
<i>A. litoralis</i>	1.82	1.45	0.43	0.28	0.30	91.18	2.00
<i>A. pseudolutosus</i>	1.28	1.35	0.32	0.21	0.23	59.31	0.00
<i>A. aegerita</i>	0.45	1.04	0.03	0.02	0.03	5.39	0.00
<i>A. dura</i>	0.50	1.06	0.06	0.04	0.05	11.76	1.00
<i>A. crocea</i>	1.50	1.36	0.33	0.21	0.23	71.57	0.00
<i>A. lividopallescens</i>	1.32	1.38	0.33	0.22	0.24	62.25	1.00
<i>A. vittadinii</i>	1.67	1.47	0.42	0.27	0.29	82.35	0.00
<i>P. columbinus</i>	0.73	1.16	0.14	0.10	0.13	23.04	0.00
<i>P. eryngii</i>	1.13	1.31	0.27	0.18	0.22	48.53	0.00
<i>A. bisporus</i>	1.00	1.26	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mean	1.13	1.28	0.23	0.15	0.17	45.23	0.36
Genus	Genus						
<i>Agaricus</i>	1.89	1.46	0.44	0.29	0.29	94.61	5.00
<i>Agrocybe</i>	1.18	1.29	0.27	0.17	0.19	52.45	1.00
<i>Amanita</i>	1.85	1.49	0.46	0.30	0.31	92.65	4.00
<i>Pleurotus</i>	1.40	1.39	0.34	0.23	0.26	64.22	1.00
Mean	1.58	1.41	0.38	0.25	0.26	75.98	2.75

Na: number of observed alleles, Ne: effective number of alleles, He: expected heterozygosity or gene diversity, I: Shannon's information index, uHe: unbiased expected heterozygosity, PPL: percentage of polymorphic loci, and PB: number of private bands.

Table 4.3 Genetic diversity indicators of different species and genera observed in a collection of 63 determined by data from SCoT markers

Species	Species						
	Na	Ne	I	He	uHe	PPL	PB
<i>A. campestris</i>	1.10	1.31	0.27	0.18	0.22	46.75	0.00
<i>A. litoralis</i>	1.75	1.43	0.41	0.27	0.28	87.57	1.00
<i>A. pseudolutosus</i>	1.44	1.40	0.35	0.24	0.26	68.05	0.00
<i>A. aegerita</i>	0.69	1.15	0.13	0.09	0.12	21.30	0.00
<i>A. dura</i>	0.75	1.19	0.16	0.11	0.13	27.81	0.00
<i>A. crocea</i>	1.57	1.45	0.39	0.26	0.27	76.33	0.00
<i>A. lividopallescens</i>	1.43	1.37	0.34	0.22	0.24	68.05	0.00
<i>A. vittadinii</i>	1.64	1.45	0.40	0.27	0.28	81.07	3.00
<i>P. columbinus</i>	0.46	1.05	0.05	0.03	0.04	7.69	0.00
<i>P. eryngii</i>	0.98	1.27	0.24	0.16	0.19	42.01	0.00
<i>A. bisporus</i>	0.95	1.26	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mean	1.16	1.30	0.25	0.17	0.18	47.88	0.36
Genus	Genus						
<i>Agaricus</i>	1.87	1.46	0.44	0.29	0.29	93.49	2.00
<i>Agrocybe</i>	1.24	1.34	0.30	0.20	0.22	57.40	0.00
<i>Amanita</i>	1.90	1.48	0.46	0.30	0.30	94.67	5.00
<i>Pleurotus</i>	1.31	1.36	0.32	0.22	0.24	60.95	0.00
Mean	1.58	1.41	0.38	0.25	0.26	76.63	1.75

Na: number of observed alleles, Ne: effective number of alleles, He: expected heterozygosity or gene diversity, I: Shannon's information index, uHe: unbiased expected heterozygosity, PPL: percentage of polymorphic loci, and PB: number of private bands.

4.1.1.4 Molecular variation among different species and genera of mushroom strains

Analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) was performed to evaluate the genetic variation among the species and genera identified from mushroom samples (Table 4.4). The variance analysis of CDDP data indicated that 23.74% and 10.82% of the genetic variation stemmed from interspecific and intergeneric variations, respectively, while 76.26% and 89.18% derived from intraspecific and intrageneric variation, respectively based on the SCoT data. The PhiPT genus and species values of CDDP data were 0.11 and 0.24, respectively, whereas the PhiPT SCoT data were 0.10 and 0.21 for genus and species, respectively.

Table 4.4 Analysis of molecular variance among several species and taxa based on CDDP and SCoT marker data

Source	CDDP markers						
	Degree of freedom	Sum square	Mean square	Estimated variance	Percentage of variance	PhiPT	
Among species	10.00	893.80	89.38	10.37	23.74	0.24	
Within species	52.00	1732.93	33.33	33.33	76.26		
Total	62.00	2626.73		43.70	100.00		
Genus	Among genus	3.00	308.29	102.76	4.77	10.82	0.11
	Within genus	59.00	2318.44	39.30	39.30	89.18	
	Total	62.00	2626.73		44.07	100.00	
Source	SCoT markers						
	Degree of freedom	Sum square	Mean square	Estimated variance	Percentage of variance	PhiPT	
Among species	10.00	679.31	67.93	7.38	20.81	0.21	
Within species	52.00	1459.86	28.07	28.07	79.19		
Total	62.00	2139.17		35.45	100.00		
Genus	Among genus	3.00	242.04	80.68	3.65	10.19	0.10
	Within genus	59.00	1897.13	32.15	32.15	89.81	
	Total	62.00	2139.17		35.80	100.00	

In relation to the CDDP data, Nei's genetic distances among species ranged from 0.07 (between *Amanita vittadinii* and *Agaricus litoralis*) to 0.48 (between *Amanita lividopallescens* and *Agrocybe aegerita*) (Table 4.5), whereas Nei's genetic dissimilarity among four genera varied from 0.03 (between *Amanita* and *Agaricus*) to 0.21 (between *Pleurotus* and *Agrocybe*) (Table 4.5). In terms of the species and genera, Nei's genetic distances derived from the SCoT data revealed the greatest distance between *Pleurotus columbinus* and *Agrocybe aegerita* (0.36), while the smallest distance was noted between *Amanita vittadinii* and *Agaricus litoralis* (0.06). *Pleurotus* and *Agrocybe* exhibited the highest Nei's genetic dissimilarity at 0.16, while *Amanita* and *Agaricus* demonstrated the lowest at 0.04 (Table 4.6).

Table 4. 5 Nei's genetic distance among different species (A) and genera (B) of mushroom samples based on the CDDP data.

A											
Species	<i>A. campestris</i>	<i>A. litoralis</i>	<i>A. pseudolotosus</i>	<i>A. aegerita</i>	<i>A. dura</i>	<i>A. crocea</i>	<i>A. lividopallescens</i>	<i>A. vittadinii</i>	<i>P. columbinus</i>	<i>P. eryngii</i>	<i>A. bisporus</i>
<i>A. campestris</i>	0.00										
<i>A. litoralis</i>	0.15	0.00									
<i>A. pseudolotosus</i>	0.20	0.10	0.00								
<i>A. aegerita</i>	0.43	0.30	0.16	0.00							
<i>A. dura</i>	0.35	0.24	0.16	0.09	0.00						
<i>A. crocea</i>	0.23	0.12	0.11	0.30	0.28	0.00					
<i>A. lividopallescens</i>	0.27	0.14	0.23	0.48	0.40	0.21	0.00				
<i>A. vittadinii</i>	0.16	0.07	0.13	0.31	0.27	0.16	0.14	0.00			
<i>P. columbinus</i>	0.28	0.25	0.26	0.42	0.38	0.25	0.34	0.24	0.00		
<i>P. eryngii</i>	0.23	0.16	0.20	0.35	0.32	0.20	0.26	0.16	0.08	0.00	
<i>A. bisporus</i>	0.32	0.26	0.30	0.40	0.35	0.30	0.32	0.27	0.28	0.17	0.00

B				
Genus	<i>Agaricus</i>	<i>Agrocybe</i>	<i>Amanita</i>	<i>Pleurotus</i>
<i>Agaricus</i>	0.00			
<i>Agrocybe</i>	0.11	0.00		
<i>Amanita</i>	0.03	0.15	0.00	
<i>Pleurotus</i>	0.12	0.21	0.12	0.00

Table 4. 6 Nei's genetic distance among various species (A) and genera (B) of mushroom samples derived from the SCoT data.

A											
Species	<i>A. campestris</i>	<i>A. litoralis</i>	<i>A. pseudolotus</i>	<i>A. aegerita</i>	<i>A. dura</i>	<i>A. crocea</i>	<i>A. lividopallescens</i>	<i>A. vittadinii</i>	<i>P. columbinus</i>	<i>P. eryngii</i>	<i>A. bisporus</i>
<i>A. campestris</i>	0.00										
<i>A. litoralis</i>	0.14	0.00									
<i>A. pseudolotus</i>	0.20	0.11	0.00								
<i>A. aegerita</i>	0.31	0.22	0.15	0.00							
<i>A. dura</i>	0.29	0.18	0.16	0.11	0.00						
<i>A. crocea</i>	0.24	0.11	0.17	0.29	0.23	0.00					
<i>A. lividopallescens</i>	0.21	0.09	0.21	0.33	0.28	0.14	0.00				
<i>A. vittadinii</i>	0.20	0.06	0.14	0.26	0.22	0.14	0.10	0.00			
<i>P. columbinus</i>	0.29	0.27	0.29	0.36	0.30	0.32	0.27	0.23	0.00		
<i>P. eryngii</i>	0.27	0.15	0.16	0.25	0.22	0.24	0.21	0.15	0.16	0.00	
<i>A. bisporus</i>	0.30	0.23	0.25	0.33	0.27	0.28	0.32	0.25	0.35	0.17	0.00

B				
Genus	<i>Agaricus</i>	<i>Agrocybe</i>	<i>Amanita</i>	<i>Pleurotus</i>
<i>Agaricus</i>	0.00			
<i>Agrocybe</i>	0.10	0.00		
<i>Amanita</i>	0.04	0.11	0.00	
<i>Pleurotus</i>	0.11	0.16	0.11	0.00

4.1.1.5 Relationships and clustering of mushroom strains

The findings of the constellation and PCA plots generated from CDDP data indicated that the 63 strains were predominantly dispersed and categorized into seven principal groups (Fig.4.6A and B). The last group, designated as the seventh group and marked in red circle, encompassed the majority of strains, totaling 24 strains. The clustering and PCA plots distinctly categorized 11 species into three clades at the species level. The PCA results for mushroom species samples revealed that the first two principal components represented 46.60% and 25.80% of the variation, respectively, for a cumulative contribution rate of 72.40%. Clade I, indicated by a red line, has six species: *Agaricus campestris*, *Agaricus litoralis*, *Agaricus pseudolutosus*, *Amanita crocea*, *Amanita lividopallescens*, and *Amanita vittadinii*. Clade II possessed three species: *Pleurotus columbinus*, *Pleurotus eryngii*, and *Agaricus bisporus*. *Agrocybe aegerita* and *Agrocybe dura* constituted the third clade (Fig.4.6C, D, and E). The WRKYF1 marker displayed the most variance across the three clades, followed by the WRKY-R3, ERF2, and MADS-1 markers, while the MYB1 marker demonstrated the least variation among the three clades (Fig. 4.6F). The clustering results, as shown in Figure 4.2, led to the classification of the 63 strains into four categories, generating the four genera. The PCA results for mushroom genera samples indicated that the first two principal components accounted for 59.30% and 40.5% of the variation, respectively, generating a cumulative contribution rate of 99.80%. The initial group comprised two genera: *Amanita* and *Agaricus*. The second and third categories consisted of the *Pleurotus* and *Agrocybe* genera, respectively (Fig.4.7).

Figure 4. 6 Clustering and interrelationships among 63 strains from various species and genera of mushrooms based on the CDDP data. A and B: Constellation and PCA plots illustrating the distribution and grouping of various strains; C, D, and E: grouping and PCA plots representing the classification of separate mushroom species; F: percentage of variation recorded by CDDP marker. S1-S63 represents 63 mushroom strains.

Figure 4. 7 Clustering and interrelationships across four genera of mushrooms observed across 63 strains based on the CDDP data.

The results from the constellation and PCA plots derived from SCoT data revealed that the 63 strains were primarily distributed and classified into seven main categories (Fig. 4.8A and B). The last group, identified as the seventh group and highlighted in red, included the majority of strains, reaching 19 strains. The clustering and PCA plots clearly divided 11 species into three clades at the species level. The PCA results for mushroom species samples revealed that the first two principal components represented 45.50% and 22.30% of the variation, respectively, for a cumulative contribution rate of 67.80%. Clade I, denoted by a red line, comprises five species: *Agaricus campestris*, *Agaricus litoralis*, *Amanita crocea*, *Amanita lividopallescens*, and *Amanita vittadinii*. *Agaricus pseudolutosus*, *Agrocybe aegerita*, and *Agrocybe dura* formed clade II, indicated by the green line. Clade III, indicated by a blue line, comprised three species: *Pleurotus columbinus*, *Pleurotus eryngii*, and *Agaricus bisporus* (Fig. 4.8C, D, and E). The SCoT13 marker exhibited the highest variance (38.26%) across the three clades, followed by the SCoT21 marker (37.20%), whilst the SCoT3 marker revealed the lowest variation (26.68%) among the three clades (Fig. 4.8F). The four genera were established from the 63 strains categorized into four classifications based on the results. The PCA results for mushroom genera samples indicated that the first two principal components accounted for 70.00% and 29.99% of the variation, respectively, generating a cumulative contribution rate of 99.99%. The original group consisted of two genera: *Amanita* and *Agaricus*. The second and third categories comprised the *Pleurotus* and *Agrocybe* genera, respectively (Fig.4.9).

Figure 4. 8 Clustering and relationships among 63 strains from several species and genera of mushrooms based on the SCoT data. A and B: Constellation and PCA plots depicting the dispersion and clustering of diverse strains; C, D, and E: clustering and PCA plots displaying the classification of distinct mushroom species; F: proportion of variation documented by SCoT markers. S1-S63 denote the 63 mushroom strains.

Figure 4. 9 Grouping and relationships over four genera of mushrooms assessed 63 strains based on the SCoT data.

4.1.2 Morpho-chemical analysis of mushroom samples

4.1.2.1 Multivariate analysis of strains of different species based on morphological traits

Using cluster and PCA analyses, eight classes were produced from strains of various species (Figure 4.10 A). Considerable variation was observed in the morphological characteristics of these strains. The PCA plot's first and second axis components were responsible for 20.00% and 69.80% of the overall variation, respectively. The fact that multiple strains of the same species, obtained from various locations, were not categorized together suggests that environmental factors have an impact on strain morphology (Figure 4.10 B).

Figure 4.10 Clustering (A) and PCA (B) plots showing the distribution and grouping of various strains of different species of mushrooms.

4.1.2.2 Morphological variation in mushroom species

Morphometric features, including the fresh weight of the sample (WS), stalk length (LS), cap vertical diameter (VDH), and cap horizontal diameter (HDH), were measured for selected mushrooms from the Iraqi Kurdistan region (Table 4.7). Mean comparison results denoted significant differences among the 11 species. The measured characters ranged from 6.36 g (*Agaricus campestris*) to 73.74 g (*Amanita crocea*), from 2.37 cm (*Agaricus bisporus*) to 10.46 cm (*Amanita lividopallescens*), from 2.83 cm (*Agaricus bisporus*) to 9.12 cm (*Amanita crocea*), and from 4.27 cm (*Agaricus litoralis*) to 9.04 cm (*Pleurotus eryngii*) for WS, LS, VDH, and HDH, respectively.

Table 4. 7 Morphological measurement of eleven wild and cultivated mushroom species

Species	WS (g)	LS (cm)	VDH (cm)	HDH (cm)
<i>Amanita crocea</i>	73.74 ± 1.50a	10.28 ± 0.67a	9.12 ± 0.78ab	7.68 ± 0.72ab
<i>Amanita vittadinii</i>	60.57 ± 1.88a	6.84 ± 0.34b	9.05 ± 0.73ab	7.55 ± 0.63abc
<i>Pleurotus eryngii</i>	35.41 ± 1.66ab	5.54 ± 0.61bc	10.70 ± 0.69a	9.04 ± 0.57a
<i>Amanita lividopallescens</i>	58.54 ± 1.01a	10.46 ± 0.76a	7.07 ± 0.51bc	6.77 ± 0.37abc
<i>Pleurotus columbinus</i>	42.68 ± 1.11ab	4.61 ± 0.73bc	7.63 ± 0.90abc	6.44 ± 0.41abc
<i>Agaricus pseudolutosus</i>	13.02 ± 0.74b	3.29 ± 0.37c	7.29 ± 0.84abc	6.77 ± 0.26abc
<i>Agrocybe dura</i>	11.04 ± 1.01b	6.07 ± 0.74bc	5.67 ± 0.53bcd	4.78 ± 0.33bc
<i>Agrocybe aegerita</i>	8.18 ± 1.03b	5.41 ± 0.86bc	4.83 ± 0.37cd	4.79 ± 0.31bc
<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	28.07 ± 1.01b	4.03 ± 0.61c	4.66 ± 0.28cd	4.25 ± 0.19c
<i>Agaricus bisporus</i>	27.05 ± 0.89b	2.37 ± 0.07c	2.83 ± 0.08d	4.91 ± 0.27bc
<i>Agaricus campestris</i>	6.36 ± 0.47b	2.81 ± 0.09c	5.67 ± 0.31bcd	4.61 ± 0.28bc

WS, fresh sample weight; LS, stalk length; VDH, cap vertical diameter; HDH, cap horizontal diameter. Distinct alphabetic characters indicate statistically significant variance among the mean values (five replicates per species), as determined by Duncan's Multiple-Range Test ($p \leq 0.05$). Each value represents the mean ± standard error.

4.1.2.3 Relationship among mushroom species using morphometric traits

Hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA), principal component analysis (PCA), and scatter plot matrix were applied to search for similarities and hidden structures among samples. The results from the three approaches summarize the three clusters (Fig. 4.11). The first cluster (red color) includes three species from the genus *Amanita*: *A. crocea*, *A. vittadinii*, and *A. lividopallescens* (Fig. 4.11A, B, and D). The second cluster (green color) included three species: *P. columbinus*, *Pleurotus eryngii*, and *Agaricus pseudolutosus*. The last group (blue color) comprises five species: *Agrocybe dura*, *Agrocybe aegerita*, *Agaricus litoralis*, *Agaricus bisporus*, and *Agaricus campestris*. The first two PCA components explained 92.4% of the variability, whereas all the factors analyzed contributed significantly to the differentiation of the first component. From the analysis, it appears that the group 1 samples, which are three species of *Amanita* with high WS and LS values, had a positive loading on component 1, which was in the upper right quadrant of the plot, whereas the group 2 samples had larger cap diameter values (Fig. 4.11C and D). The largest distance measured (4.77) was between *Agrocybe dura* and *Amanita crocea*, and the smallest (0.32) was between *Agrocybe dura* and *Agrocybe aegerita* (Fig. 4.11E). The variation among the three groups accounted for by the HDH trait was the greatest (80.73%), followed by the WS trait (80.50%). In contrast, LS (71.56%) and VDH (71.67%) showed the least variation among the three groups (Fig. 4.11F). As shown in Fig. 4.10D, the four morphometric features were not strong enough to completely separate the three groups.

Figure 4.11 Relationships among mushroom species based on morphometric features. A: Clustering of species using the AHC method; B: Clustering of species using PCA plot; C: Distribution of studied traits using PCA method; D: Grouping of mushroom species using scatter plot; E: Genetic distance among mushroom species; F: Variation percentage explained by each trait for separation of the three groups.

4.1.2.4 Assessment of bioactive content differentiation in mushroom species

The present study results showed that the approximate composition of 11 mushroom species is presented in Table 4.8. All biochemical traits were observed, and a statistically significant difference was detected among all 11 species. In terms of fresh weight, total phenolic content (TPC) had a broad range of 121.89 to 253.85 $\mu\text{g/g}$. In this study, *Agaricus litoralis*, *Agrocybe aegerita*, and *Agaricus campestris* had the highest TPC levels, with TPC values of 253.85, 237.94, and 232.06 $\mu\text{g/g}$, respectively. *Agrocybe dura* on the other spectrum registered 121.89 TPC. Antioxidant activity (DPPH) ranged from 237.84 to 575.92 $\mu\text{g/g}$. *Agaricus litoralis* exhibited the highest DPPH activity at 575.92 $\mu\text{g/g}$, whereas *A. dura* exhibited the lowest DPPH activity of 237.84 $\mu\text{g/g}$. All mushroom species showed various total flavonoids (TFC) ranging from 16.40 to 44.63 $\mu\text{g/g}$. *Agaricus bisporus* recorded a TFC of 16.40 $\mu\text{g/g}$, whereas *Agaricus pseudolutosus*, *Agrocybe aegerita*, and *Amanita vittadinii* recorded 44.63, 40.70, and 40.47 $\mu\text{g/g}$ of TFC respectively. The highest moisture content (MC) recorded was 94.17% for *Agaricus bisporus*. In our comparison, the proportion of dry matter (DM) ranges from 5.83 to 11.92%. The highest MC (54.12%) was obtained for *Agaricus campestris*, whereas the lowest DM (5.83% and 6.19%) was obtained for *A. bisporus* and *A. pseudolutosus*, respectively. Minor variations in protein content (PC) and soluble sugars (SSC) were observed among the different mushroom species. The highest levels of PC and SSC were detected in *Amanita crocea* (5.01 mg/g) and *Pleurotus eryngii* (1.12 $\mu\text{g/g}$), respectively.

Table 4. 8 Biochemical content differences among 11 mushroom samples collected from different locations in Iraqi Kurdistan.

Species	TPC ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW)	DPPH ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW)	TFC ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW)	MC (%)	DM (%)	PC (mg/g FW)	SSC ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW)
<i>Agaricus litoralis</i>	253.85 \pm 2.13a	575.92 \pm 3.27a	34.81 \pm 1.44ab	88.73 \pm 1.79c	11.27 \pm 0.52a	4.79 \pm 0.48a	0.71 \pm 0.09b
<i>Agrocybe aegerita</i>	237.94 \pm 2.53ab	411.59 \pm 2.56ab	40.70 \pm 1.78ab	90.05 \pm 1.11bc	9.95 \pm 0.43ab	4.29 \pm 0.56a	1.00 \pm 0.08a
<i>Amanita lividopallescens</i>	142.61 \pm 1.09ab	398.07 \pm 2.72ab	35.60 \pm 1.23ab	92.61 \pm 1.72ab	7.39 \pm 0.52bc	4.70 \pm 0.53a	0.79 \pm 0.06b
<i>Agaricus pseudolutosus</i>	158.30 \pm 1.56ab	284.35 \pm 1.29b	44.63 \pm 1.99a	93.81 \pm 1.01a	6.19 \pm 0.42c	4.57 \pm 0.44a	0.25 \pm 0.03c
<i>Amanita crocea</i>	146.76 \pm 2.03ab	363.37 \pm 2.19ab	33.60 \pm 1.11ab	90.19 \pm 1.28bc	9.81 \pm 0.32ab	5.01 \pm 0.41a	0.75 \pm 0.08b
<i>Pleurotus eryngii</i>	156.97 \pm 1.71ab	268.94 \pm 2.67b	34.44 \pm 1.16ab	88.62 \pm 1.96c	11.38 \pm 0.54a	4.43 \pm 0.61a	1.12 \pm 0.07a
<i>Agaricus campestris</i>	232.06 \pm 2.36 ab	379.75 \pm 3.27ab	37.25 \pm 1.22ab	88.08 \pm 1.25c	11.92 \pm 0.25a	3.87 \pm 0.29a	0.56 \pm 0.03b
<i>Amanita vittadinii</i>	128.57 \pm 1.37ab	276.12 \pm 2.27b	40.47 \pm 1.12ab	92.80 \pm 1.89ab	7.20 \pm 0.58bc	4.36 \pm 0.48a	0.64 \pm 0.07b
<i>Pleurotus columbinus</i>	142.25 \pm 2.13ab	279.16 \pm 2.38b	31.23 \pm 1.44b	92.76 \pm 1.28ab	7.24 \pm 0.45bc	4.33 \pm 0.40a	1.10 \pm 0.08a
<i>Agrocybe dura</i>	207.71 \pm 2.09ab	244.53 \pm 2.57b	32.82 \pm 1.77b	92.73 \pm 1.28ab	7.27 \pm 0.39bc	4.40 \pm 0.37a	0.97 \pm 0.06a
<i>Agaricus bisporus</i>	121.89 \pm 1.24b	237.84 \pm 19.89b	16.40 \pm 0.67c	94.17 \pm 1.99a	5.83 \pm 0.22c	1.37 \pm 0.24 b	0.25 \pm 0.03c

TPC, total phenolic content; TFC, total flavonoid content; DPPH, antioxidant activity; MC, moisture content; DM, dry matter; PC, protein content; SSC, soluble sugar content. Different letters denote statistically significant differences between mean values (three replicates per species), as shown by Duncan's multiple range test ($p \leq 0.05$). Each value represents the mean \pm standard error.

4.1.2.5 Multivariate assessment of strains from numerous species according to their biochemical properties

According to the biochemical traits shown in the constellation and PCA plots, the different strains of different species were divided into four main groups. There were many strains in the fourth group, which was red in color (Figure 4.12A and B). For both the first and second axes, the PCA plot's components contributed 35.10% and 25.50% of the overall variation, respectively. Within a single species, a notable expansion and dispersion of strains was noted (Figure 4.12C). The biochemical characteristics of the *Agaricus litoralis* strains showed the most variation, indicating the impact of environmental factors on the accumulation of bioactive compounds. Elevated levels of PC, TPC, and antioxidant activity (DPPH) distinguish the first group (brown color). The second group, represented by blue, is marked by high levels of SSC and DM (Figure 4.12D).

4.1.2.6 Analysis of relationships among mushroom species using biochemical markers

The data obtained from the AHC, PCA, and scatter matrix methods were condensed into three clusters (Fig. 4.13A-E). The first cluster (red) covered five species: *Amanita crocea*, *Plerotus eryngii*, *Agaricus campestris*, *Agaricus litoralis*, and *A. aegerita*. The second cluster (green) contained five species: *Amanita vittadinii*, *Amanita lividopallescens*, *Pleurotus columbinus*, *Agrocybe dura*, and *Agaricus pseudolutosus*. The final group (blue) includes the cultivated species, *Agaricus bisporus*. The first two PCA components accounted for 75.9% of variability. Based on the PCA plots in Fig. 4.13B, C, and D, it seems that the first AHC group of samples had high values of TPC, DPPH, TFC, DM, PC, and SSC, which had a positive loading on the first component in the right quadrant of the plot, and AHC group 2 samples had larger values of MC (Fig. 4.13C and D). The variation among the three groups accounted for by the PC trait was the greatest at 94.49%, followed by DM (91.03%) and MC (91.03%). In contrast, the SSC trait showed the least variation (25.39 %) among the three groups (Fig. 4.13F). The greatest distance recorded (5.11) was between *Amanita lividopallescens* and *Agaricus litoralis*, while the smallest distance (0.48) was between *Agrocybe dura* and *Plerotus columbinus* (Fig. 4.13G). During this analysis, MC and DM clearly separated the mushrooms into three group.

Figure 4.12. Multivariate analysis of different strains according to biochemical characteristics. A. constellation diagram showing multiple strains clustered together. B and C. PCA plots exhibiting the spreading of different strains of various species. D. PCA plots showing the distribution of biochemical traits on the first and second components.

Figure 4.13 Relationships between mushroom species and biochemical parameters. A: Clustering of species using the AHC method; B and C: Clustering of species using PCA plot; D: Distribution of studied traits using PCA method; E: Grouping of mushroom species using scatter plot; F: Variation percentage explained by each trait for the separation of three groups; and G: Genetic distance among mushroom species.

4.1.2.7 Chemical composition profile and compounds relationship of different extracts

From the GC/MS analysis depicted in Fig. 4.14 and the (Fig. 4.19), it can be seen that the number of detected compounds ranged between 8 and 76 bioactive compounds. The maximum number of detected compounds was recorded in *Pleurotus*, with 76 compounds in *Pleurotus eryngii* and 74 compounds in *Pleurotus columbinus*, whereas the minimum number of compounds was found in the cultivated species: *A. bisporus* (8) and *A. litoralis* (15).

The concentrations of the primary compounds of *Agrocybe aegerita*, *Agrocybe dura*, *Agaricus campestris*, *Amanita crocea*, *Pleurotus eryngii*, *Amanita lividopallescens*, *Pleurotus columbinus*, *Agaricus pseudolutosus*, *Amanita vittadinii*, *Agaricus bisporus*, and *Agaricus litoralis* were determined to be 1.03 (C14) to 20.79% (C18), 1.16 (C8) to 34.63% (C11), 1.47 (C4) to 26.88% (C3), 1.26 (C4) to 12.44% (C10), 1.03 (C2) to 12.43% (C18), 1.07 (C3) to 16.56% (C15), 1.01 (C12) to 14.50% (C17), 1.02 (C2) to 17.07% (C8), 1.06 (C1) to 19.11% (C15), 1.52 (C3) to 85.67% (C1), and 1.29 (C8) to 55.82% (C6), respectively (Fig. 4.15 and Appendix 3). Many different compounds were identified in the extracts of the 11 species, including five prevalent compounds, namely 9-octadecenoic acid, 13-octadecenoic acid-methyl ester, ergosterol, hexadecanoic acid-methyl ester, and hexadecanoic acid (Fig. 4.16A-E). For *A. lividopallescens*, the highest concentrations of 9-octadecenoic acid (16.56%), 13-octadecenoic acid-methyl ester (11.15%), ergosterol (14.62%), and hexadecanoic acid-methyl ester (10.13%) were observed, whereas *Amanita vittadinii* had the highest concentration of hexadecanoic acid (15.22%), followed by *Agaricus litoralis* (13.08%). *Agaricus bisporus* had the lowest values for 9-octadecenoic acid, 13-octadecenoic acid-methyl ester, ergosterol, and hexadecanoic acid-methyl ester. Based on the common compounds, a PCA model was created to identify the most important variables that explained the connections among the 11 mushroom species and to establish group patterns (Fig. 4.17).

The first two principal components, which accounted for 90.80% of the total variability (70.40% and 20.40% for PC1 and PC2, respectively), divided the studied species into three groups (Fig. 4.17A). The first group (marked in blue) consisted of four species: *Amanita crocea*, *Amanita lividopallescens*, *Pleurotus columbinus*, and *Pleurotus eryngii*. The second group (marked in green) comprised two species: *Amanita vittadinii* and *Agaricus litoralis*. The last group (marked in red) was comprised of five species: *Agrocybe aegerita*, *Agrocybe dura*, *Agaricus campestris*, *Agaricus pseudolutosus*, and *Agaricus bisporus*. The first principal component was clearly identified as hexadecanoic acid-methyl ester (C2), ergosterol (C3), 13-octadecenoic acid-methyl ester (C4), and 9-octadecenoic acid (C5), while the second principal component was related to n-hexadecanoic acid (C1) (Fig. 4.17B).

Figure 4. 14 Number of compounds detected by GC/MS in 11 mushroom species.

Figure 4.15 Concentrations of the major compounds detected in 11 mushroom species. A: *A. aegerita*, B: *A. dura*, C: *A. campestris*, D: *A. crocea*, E: *P. eryngii*, F: *A. lividopallescens*, G: *P. columbine*, H: *A. pseudolutosus*, I: *A. vittadinii*, J: *A. bisporus*, and K: *A. litoralis*. The names of the compounds (labelled C) are provided in appendix 3.

Figure 4. 16 Concentration percentages of some common compounds in mushroom species. A: 9-Octadecenoic acid, B: 13-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester, C: Ergosterol, D: Hexadecanoic acid methyl ester, and E: Hexadecanoic acid.

Figure 4. 17 Relationship between the studied species and common compounds. A: Distribution of different species on the PCA plot, B: Distribution of common compounds on the two axes of the PCA plot. C1-C5 represent common compounds: C1: n-hexadecanoic acid, C2: hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester, C3: ergosterol, C4: 13-octadecenoic acid, methyl ester, and C5: 9-octadecenoic acid, (E)-.

4.1.2.8 Correlation among mushroom species based on the morpho-biochemical characters

The morpho-biochemical traits and common major compound correlation relationships were analyzed using Spearman's correlation method. Results revealed nineteen significant correlations between traits, with three exhibiting a negative relationship (Fig. 4.18). Hexadecanoic acid-methyl ester (C2) showed a strong positive correlation with ergosterol (C3), 13-octadecenoic acid-methyl ester (C4), and 9-octadecenoic acid (C5) with the values of 0.81**, 0.99**, and 0.84**, respectively. The same was true for 9-octadecenoic acid (C5) and 13-octadecenoic acid-methyl ester (C4), which were positively correlated (0.85**). The case of ergosterol (C3) positively correlated with 9-octadecenoic acid (C5) and 13-octadecenoic acid-methyl ester (C4) was 0.80** and 0.68*, respectively. WS was positively associated with LS (0.76**) and HDH (0.64*). Similarly, there was a strong positive correlation between VDH and HDH (0.93**). A moderate negative correlation of VDH (-0.64*) and HDH (-0.65*) with TPC was stated. The TFC was positively correlated with PC, which was 0.79**. LS was positively correlated with C2 (0.76**), C3 (0.68*), C4 (0.78**), and C5 (0.68*).

Figure 4. 18 A heatmap showing the correlation among morpho-biochemical features.

4.1.2.9 Beneficial and risky health of mushroom species

Mushrooms are known to possess medicinal properties. In addition, they are low in fat and high in protein and vitamin contents. They are also an excellent source of minerals and other dietary fibers. Specific biochemical agents in mushrooms are what make them beneficial to humans. Such bioactive agents include polysaccharides, triterpenoids, low molecular weight proteins, glycoproteins, and immunomodulating compounds (Assemie and Abaya, 2022). According to the data of this study, mushrooms serve as a great source of nutraceuticals, along with many other benefits, such as anticancer, prebiotic, immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, cardiovascular, antimicrobial, and antidiabetic effects (Appendix 3). However, current research has detected potentially hazardous chemicals that are non-carcinogenic and cancerous in extracts from different species, which pose risks to human health, as highlighted in (Tables 4.9 and 4.10.)

Table 4. 9 Concentrations of different potentially dangerous chemical constituents detected during the analysis of mushroom extracts from different species.

Toxic compounds	<i>A. aegerita</i>	<i>A. dura</i>	<i>A. campestris</i>	<i>A. crocea</i>	<i>P. eryngii</i>	<i>A. lividopallescens</i>	<i>P. columbinus</i>	<i>A. pseudolutosus</i>	<i>A. vittadini</i>	<i>A. bisporus</i>	<i>A. litoralis</i>
4-Methyl-2,4-bis(p-hydroxyphenyl) pent-1-ene, 2TMS derivative	-	34.63	1.67	11.22	4.90	-	-	-	5.18	5.45	-
Carbonyl sulfide	-	-	26.88	-	-	-	-	-	5.99	-	-
Methane-d, trichloro-	-	-	-	1.26	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Benzene, 1-methyl-2-nitroso-	-	-	-	-	1.03	-	-	-	-	-	-
Conhydrin	-	-	-	-	-	1.43	-	-	-	-	-
6,8-Dodecadien-1-ol (6Z,8E)	-	-	-	-	-	3.36	-	-	-	-	-
Ethane, 1,2-dibromo-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.29	-	-	-
Tolycaine	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	17.07	-	-	-

Table 4. 10 Health risk of chemical components presents in extracts from various species of mushrooms.

Compounds	Health risk	References
4-Methyl-2,4-bis(p-hydroxyphenyl) pent-1-ene, 2TMS derivative	Hormonal activities, toxic effects on insulin-producing cells in the pancreas, strong estrogen-like properties that could affect the progression of breast cancer, and harmful impacts on pulmonary function through the promotion of cell death	(Huang, C.-C. et al., 2021; Liu, Su, Lee, & Chen, 2016)
Carbonyl sulfide	Characteristics of thiocarbamate herbicides. These compounds are metabolized into hydrogen sulfide, a substance capable of inducing harmful effects on cellular respiration and causing neurotoxicity	(Andrew R. Bartholomaeus & Victoria S. Haritos, 2005; DeMartino, Zigler, Fukuto, & Ford, 2017)
Methane-d, trichloro-	Toxicological effects	(Lontoh & Semrau, 1998b)
Benzene, 1-methyl-2-nitroso-	Genotoxicity and carcinogenic potential	(Noriega, Cardoso-Ortiz, López-Luna, Del Cuevas-Flores, & La Flores De Torre, Juan Armando, 2022)
Conhydrin	Neurotoxic properties	(Hotti & Rischer, 2017)
6,8-Dodecadien-1-ol (6Z,8E)	Potential applications in pest management	(Bahetjan et al., 2023a)
Ethane, 1,2-dibromo-	Genotoxic effects leading to carcinogenic potential	(Iyer & Makris, 2010)
Tolycaine	Anesthetic, convulsions, and potential antimicrobial properties	(Sawaki et al., 2000)

Figure 4. 19 GC/MS chromatogram of methanolic extracts obtained from 11 mushroom species. A: *A. aegerita*, B: *A. dura*, C: *A. campestris*, D: *A. crocea*, E: *P. eryngii*, F: *A. lividopallescens*, G: *P. columbinus*, H: *A. pseudolutosus*, I: *A. vittadinii*, J: *A. bisporus*, K: *A. litoralis*.

Figure 4. 19 (continued, caption shown on previous page)

4.2. Discussion

4.2.1 Molecular analysis

Research on any kind of organism cannot proceed without first establishing an accurate taxonomy. Conventional mushroom identification relies on morphological characteristics such as fruitbody size, shape, length, diameter, and any other distinguishing characteristics. The contradiction in macrofungi taxonomy at the species and genus levels has been corroborated by the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region of nuclear ribosomal DNA, encompassing ITS1 and ITS4. The current study involves the PCR product of mushrooms, measuring roughly 550-750 base pairs. Fujita *et al.*, (2001) documented fragment sizes ranging from 350 to 880 bp for fungi using ITS1 and ITS4. Following PCR amplification using ITS1 and ITS4 primers, Adeniyi *et al.*, (2018) reported a product of approximately 850 bp. This study attempted to resolve the phylogenetic relationship of the 63 strains invested in the region of Iraqi Kurdistan using the ITS rDNA. Eleven species distributed in four genera were revealed by this study from the collected samples of wild mushrooms. The second group of this study included strains from the genera *Agaricus*, *Amanita*, and *Agrocybe*, whereas the *Pleurotus* strains were placed in the first group. The strains of species in the *Amanita* genus were stratified in the beginning sub-group of the second group. Subsequently, the species which were placed under the genera *Agaricus* and *Agrocybe* were clustered together with the same secondary subgroup.

The second group also consists of the cultivated mushroom *Agaricus bisporus*. The ITS region of the strains in the same clade group was, however, highly homogenous within the group, which is the reason for putting them grouped together (Stackebrandt *et al.*, 2002). Moreover, the bootstrap in this investigation was 9 and 100%. The BLASTn analysis of the ITS data showed that the dominant strains in all the identified mushroom samples corresponded to *Agaricus litoralis*, followed by *Amanita vittadinii* and *Amanita crocea*, which indicates that the species adapt to different environments. Understanding genetic diversity within and between species or genera is essential for creating efficient conservation management strategies for endangered and threatened species. There is a broad and varied genetic availability of wild mushroom strains in Iraqi Kurdistan. In order to find resources, find new genes, and breed new types, it is essential to study the genetic diversity of germplasms. Since critical mushroom species are still rarely bred, most cultivated strains are derived from tamed wild varieties. Problems like recurrent strains and unclear genetic links across varieties emerged as a consequence of the limitations in genetic diversity between parent strains brought about by isolating tissue culture and rebranding. Genomic research into the relationships between wild mushroom strains collected from various parts of Iraqi Kurdistan is crucial. Future breeding and use of germplasm also necessitate genetic diversity studies among strains (Gu *et al.*, 2024; Tahir *et al.*, 2015). Conventional molecular markers may not consistently elucidate phenotypic variations as

effectively as genetic diversity assessment using CDDP and SCoT. There has been no prior mention of applying CDDP and SCoT to create fingerprints of wild mushroom germplasm for the analysis of genetic associations (Gao *et al.*, 2018). Fungi typically exhibit significant levels of genetic variety in their wild populations when they are sexually reproducing, inhabiting diverse ecological niches, and/or found all over the world. This investigation used two different types of molecular markers to generate 373 bands. Comparatively, SCoT primers detected 14.08 polymorphic bands from various markers, but CDDP primers averaged 17 bands. Polymorphism in various parts of the mushroom's genome likely causes this variation, which is contributed to SCoT markers that specifically target the highly conserved region surrounding the start codon (ATG) in mushroom genes, while CDDP markers amplify portions of conserved functional genes (transcription factors). The high levels of polymorphism exhibited by various markers clearly indicated their applicability in genetic variability investigations in wild mushroom strains, and they could be used to identify plant materials that are related in different species and genera (Golian *et al.*, 2022b; Khandayataray *et al.*, 2022).

Gene diversity determines the degree of genetic variety within breeding population accessions. The primary focus here are the evolutionary restrictions on alleles and the probable mutation rate for a certain locus. Genomic diversity reflects genetic diversity for haploid markers and provides an estimate of anticipated heterozygosity and genetic distance among population members (Salem and Sallam, 2016). Our research indicates that CDDP and SCoT markers are effective for assessing genetic diversity in mushroom samples and validating the presence of significant genetic variation. In this investigation, the use of SCoT and CDDP markers with polymorphic variation possessed higher PIC parameters. This allowed for efficient selection of the most appropriate markers for the research on genetic divergence. A diversity index allows assigning strain members to different groups, enabling a quantitative measure of the diversity of the species or genus range. Variegated indices are used to indicate the differing degrees of diversity, where lower values indicate low diversity while higher values suggest high diversity (Oluyinka Christopher, 2020). There is a notable amount of variability in SCoT genome analysis between species. For instance, Shannon's information index mean value 'I' which is calculated from SCoT markers, is more than that which is computed from CDDP markers, suggesting that there exist much variation and ecological complexity impacts on the SCoT loci target area. Expected heterozygosity or gene diversity values were mostly low for both species and genera for most markers, supporting the evidence from AMOVA analysis of high diversity among various species. Average gene diversity values for four genera of mushrooms were higher than those of 11 species of mushrooms: 0.30 for both markers versus 0.17 and 0.18 for CDDP and SCoT, respectively. Results of AMOVA analysis demonstrated that the PhiPT value for CDDP data was higher than that of the SCoT marker, which means that CDDP markers are more informative than the SCoT approach for revealing the variation between different taxa. Mushroom species require

molecular markers for genetic characterization in order to better understand the variety of mushrooms available and develop strategies for their breeding. Markers assist in research and cultivation, as well as in the determination of specific genetic loci and their associated bands (Khatun *et al.*, 2017; Lee *et al.*, 2019; Singh and Gupta, 2017). With CDDP data, our study found that the genus *Agaricus* had the largest number of unique bands (5), while the genus *Amanita* had only four. On the other hand, SCoT data identified four maximum specific bands linked to the *Amanita* genus. This study postulates that these unique bands associated with the *Agaricus* genus could potentially serve as biomarkers for differentiating strains of mushrooms across different taxa. In addition, these unique bands can be linked to phenotypic and other enhancements, and to the construction of a new marker that evaluates genetic diversity (Jiao *et al.*, 2024; Liu *et al.*, 2022) .

Cluster analyses are important in aiding interspecies mapping investigations because they assist in understanding genetic diversity (Eltaher *et al.*, 2018a) . The dendrogram produced confirms a large diversity of mushroom strains and taxa. The diversity among strains, species, and genera points to an abundance of genetic material and an elevated amount of genetic variation. The CDDP markers had a wider spectrum of dissimilarities than the SCoT markers, indicating a high degree of structural variability in transcription factor genes. It was considered more effective to discriminate between the strains of different taxa and genera using markers CDDP and SCoT. The *Agaricus litoralis* isolates located within the Basneh region were determined from the CDDP plot (group 1; olive circle), while those found in the Penjwen region belonged to group 5 (mint circle). All *Agaricus pseudolutosus* strains were ranged within the same group (group 3; teal circle). The isolates of *Amanita vittadinii* were positioned in two groups: group 2 (purple circle) and group 5 (blue circle). The different SCoT markers used in the clustering plot depicted the allocation of strains of different species and genera into different clades; for example, the *Agaricus litoralis* strains collected from different areas of the regions were arranged in clades 3 and 4. The differences existing among strains of a particular mushroom species collected from different regions can be largely accounted for by the different environmental conditions of those regions. These environmental factors have an influence on not only the growth of mushrooms but also their productivity as well as the genetic diversity and adaptability of the fungi (Bellettini *et al.*, 2019; Vieira *et al.*, 2022) . This diversity in strains distribution denotes a considerable level of genetic variation existing among members of the same taxa. One of the reasons for the discrepancy between the CDDP and SCoT clustering, as well as with the ITS method, is that different techniques increase the genomic variation of the different strains of the same taxon and genus. Gap spacer DNA that is amplified by the universal barcode sequence (ITS) separates the large subunit rRNA from the small subunit rRNA genes on the chromosome. SCoT markers focus on the highly conserved area not far from the ATG in the fungal genes, while CDDP markers focus on the

regions of conserved functional genes, which are transcription factors (Khal *et al.*, 2023; Tahir *et al.*, 2023).

4.2.2 Morpho-chemical analysis

Numerous studies have demonstrated that extracts from various mushroom species contain substantial amounts of bioactive compounds such as phenols, flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, tannins, steroids, and cardiac glycosides and these compounds have been linked to a range of biological activities (Assemie and Abaya, 2022; Fogarasi *et al.*, 2024). The composition of cultivated mushroom species is well documented; however, wild edible mushrooms remain under-researched, and to our knowledge, the bioactive contents of ten wild species have not been previously reported. Wild mushrooms exhibit higher levels of soluble carbohydrates (SSC) and protein content (PC) than cultivated varieties (*Agaricus bisporus*). Furthermore, significant variations in SSC and PC were observed among different wild mushroom species. These differences can be attributed to several factors, including the genetic composition and environmental conditions of mushroom growth (Stojek *et al.*, 2024). Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are major contributors to various health issues, making the search for natural antioxidants crucial. Phenolic compounds play a significant role in antioxidant activity, with mushroom extracts showing a strong correlation between the phenolic content and antioxidant properties (Effiong *et al.*, 2024; Ruth *et al.*, 2022).

Our study of 11 species has revealed substantial differences in biochemical contents. Wild mushroom species had higher total phenolic content (TPC), total flavonoid content (TFC), and antioxidant activity (DPPH) than their cultivated counterparts, which may be attributed to genetic makeup, geographical, and environmental factors. The results indicated an inverse relationship between total phenolic content (TPC) and cap diameter growth, suggesting that high phenolic accumulation inhibits cap expansion (Ashti *et al.*, 2018; Tahir *et al.*, 2024). Generally, low levels of certain phenolic compounds can positively affect growth, but their effects are detrimental at high concentrations. Earlier, some researchers studied the morphology and biochemical and biological activity of a number of mushrooms species, and a variety of results were obtained with respect to species and environmental conditions (Chaudhary *et al.*, 2023; Chechan *et al.*, 2020; Hayat *et al.*, 2024; Khumlianlal *et al.*, 2022; Krümmel *et al.*, 2022; Ouali *et al.*, 2023; Senila *et al.*, 2024). A positive correlation was observed between stalk length (LS) and several common major compounds, including 9-octadecenoic acid, 13-octadecenoic acid-methyl ester, ergosterol, and hexadecanoic acid-methyl ester. The current scientific literature lacks extensive documentation on the correlation between mushroom stalk length and the presence of certain compounds. Cultivated mushroom varieties exhibit a higher moisture content than their wild counterparts. This increase in moisture content decreases the nutritional value (Bhardwaj *et al.*, 2024).

The decrease in water content and increase in the accumulation of dry matter in wild mushrooms suggest higher levels of bioactive compounds, which subsequently increase the overall quality of mushrooms. The dependency of species and the environmental context of the organism bring about an important relationship between phytochemical compounds such as TPC, TFC, and antioxidant activity.

In this study, PC and TFC were found to be positively correlated. Increased protein levels may be associated with changes in the concentration of flavonoids, suggesting that high protein levels may include those associated with flavonoid biosynthesis. Cluster analysis plays a crucial role in facilitating interspecific mapping studies by enhancing our understanding of genetic diversity (Eltaher *et al.*, 2018b). A dendrogram and PCA plot revealed a significant variety of mushroom taxa. This species diversity suggests a rich genetic pool and a high level of genetic variation. Along with morphological features, the horizontal cap diameter emerged as the most distinguishing feature among the three clusters. Similarly, dry matter and protein content were the most useful biochemical traits that were differentiated the three clusters obtained from the biochemical data. GC/MS appraisal showed that the wild species had more identified compounds than their cultivated species, which was not surprising. This species difference may be due to the genetic composition and environmental features of the biotopes of wild species, which are sometimes considered stressful (Munir *et al.*, 2023). The main compounds found in various species of mushrooms, especially in wild ones, exhibit multidimensional biological and pharmaceutical attributes, including antimicrobial, antioxidant, cytotoxic, antitumor, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, and antiandrogenic activities. The activities of these compounds have been well clarified through extensive research. Hexadecanoic acid demonstrated anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties (Ganesan *et al.*, 2024; Shaaban *et al.*, 2021). The methyl ester of 13-octadecenoic acid exhibits antioxidant, hypocholesterolemic, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer activities (Krishnamoorthy and Subramaniam, 2014). Research has shown that 9-octadecenoic acid offers multiple health benefits. It has been found to improve cardiovascular health, reduce inflammation, inhibit cancer growth, enhance immune system function, and protect nerve cells. These diverse effects highlight the compound's potential therapeutic applications across various medical fields (Piccinin *et al.*, 2019b). Ergosterol, another compound of interest, maintains membrane integrity, acts as a precursor of vitamin D2, exhibits antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory actions, and exerts neuroprotective effects (Rangsinth *et al.*, 2023).

Due to its minimal sugar content, *A. pseudolutosus* and *A. bisporus* may be beneficial for people struggling with obesity, diabetes, or heart-related issues. The rising incidence of mushroom poisoning has become a notable health concern, as indicated by the growing number of worldwide reports (Nieminen and Mustonen, 2020a). Eight toxic compounds were found in the listed species using GC/MS analysis, which included the following: 4-Methyl-2-4-bis(o-hydroxyphenyl) pent-1-ene

2TMS derivative, carbonyl sulfide, methane-d, trichloro-, benzene, 1-methyl-2-nitroso-, conhydrin, 6,8-Dodecadien-1-ol (6Z,8E), ethane, 1,2-dibromo-and tolycaine. These substances exhibit estrogenic activity, thiocarbamate herbicide properties, neurotoxicity, genotoxic and carcinogenic potentials, anesthetic effects, and convulsant properties.

Conclusions

The following are the main findings of this study:

- CDDP and SCoT markers, along with the ITS gene, can perform phylogenetic analysis which can accurately classify mushroom sample species by their genetic variation levels.
- Molecular phylogenetic analysis was found to be useful for tracing the relationships of the sixty-three strains of mushrooms from the Iraqi Kurdistan region.
- According to the clustering analysis, there is a high level of divergence at both the species and genus levels.
- The species of mushrooms displayed the presence of AT content in greater quantities compared to the GC content.
- The genetic relationships of mushroom samples at the strain, species, and genus levels are highly facilitated by the CDDP and SCoT markers, which are very efficient in polymorphism detection. The results verified the possibility of markers CDDP and SCoT being able to differentiate strains of the same species from different regions.
- This research has shown that edible mushrooms are an excellent source of nutrients, including proteins, dietary fibers, and secondary metabolites. The evaluated wild mushrooms had high levels of total phenolics content (TPC), total content of flavonoids (TFC), antioxidant activity (DPPH), protein content (PC), dry matter content (DM), ergosterol, and fatty acids.
- The potential toxicity observed in these representative wild mushroom species necessitates caution regarding their regular consumption, as the accumulation of these toxic compounds may result in various adverse health outcomes.
- *Agaricus litoralis*, *Pleurotus Columbinus* and *Agrocybe aegerita* were especially distinguishable as dietary and health beneficial mushrooms, as they had the highest TPC, TFC, DDPH, and PC contents but low amounts of fatty acids and their derivatives. Notably, there are no potentially harmful toxins in these species, which makes them suitable for human nutrition.

Recommendations

This study makes several important suggestions, including:

- There are still a lot of unstudied wild mushroom species in Iraqi Kurdistan, thus further research is required to identify new species.
- The composition, taxonomy, and biological activities of edible wild and cultivated mushrooms from the Iraqi Kurdistan region were all included in this study. For the sustainable management of these priceless bioresources, integrated solutions are therefore required. This includes preserving these resources and their environments, enhancing commercially profitable cultural practices, and evaluating biotechnological potential.
- Additional studies focused on the heavy metal accumulation in mushroom samples should be performed.
- Studies should examine how overharvesting and habitat loss affect the diversity of wild mushrooms, suggesting conservation measures and sustainable collection quotas.
- There should be a greater push to domesticate and raise rare or valuable wild species in controlled environments.
- Creating value-added products (such as supplements, extracts, and powders) to increase the market for mushrooms that are collected from the wild.
- To bring these natural resources into the mainstream of pharmaceutical use, future development of medications derived from bioactive compounds found in wild mushrooms will require cooperative research, technological innovation, and clinical validation.

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